

YAŞAR UNIVERSITY
GRADUATE SCHOOL

MASTER IN ART THESIS

**FRAMING OF THE 2021 ISRAEL GAZA CONFLICT: A
CONTENT ANALYSIS OF HAARETZ.COM NEWS
COVERAGE**

ZOHAIR RAZA

THESIS ADVISOR: ASSOC. PROF. (PHD) GIZEM MELEK

MA, COMMUNICATION

PRESENTATION DATE: 20TH JUNE 2023

BORNOVA / İZMİR
JUNE 2023

We certify that, as the jury, we have read this thesis and that in our opinion it is fully adequate, in scope and in quality, as a thesis for the degree of MA Communication.

Jury Members:

Signature:

Assoc. Prof. (PhD) Gizem Melek
Yasar University

.....

Assoc. Prof. (PhD) Dilek Melike Uluçay
Yasar University

.....

Prof. (PhD) Burak Doğu
Izmir University of Economics

.....

Prof. (PhD) Xxx YYY
Director of the Graduate School

ABSTRACT

FRAMING OF THE 2021 ISRAEL GAZA CONFLICT: A CONTENT ANALYSIS OF HAARETZ.COM NEWS COVERAGE

Raza, Zohair

Master of Arts, Communication

Advisor: Assoc. Prof. (PhD) Gizem MELEK

June 2023

In this study, the aim was to observe the reporting pattern and methodology employed by *Haaretz*, an Israeli newspaper of international repute, during the 2021 Haram Al-Shareef conflict between the state of Israel, *Hamas*, Israeli far-right and Israeli minorities. This conflict was selected because of its peculiar nature due to its multi-faceted participation from all sides and not just *Hamas*. The observations were quantified using the content analysis measure for frames developed by Semetko & Valkenburg (2000a). The results revealed that, despite the rise in the usage of Imagefare (Image Warfare) by the conflicting parties, *Haaretz* did not shy away from criticizing the government and state institutions. It also employed reporters from *Gaza* to bypass the information blackouts by the Israeli Defense Forces (IDF), usually during the times of conflict.

keywords: Framing, Media Coverage, Haram Al Shareef, Israel, Haaretz, IDF, Hamas, Arab-Israelis, Israeli-Far Right.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to acknowledge my gratitude for my advisor, Professor Gizem, for her unwavering support throughout my thesis and for her patience.

Zohair Raza

İzmir, 2023

TEXT OF OATH

I declare and honestly confirm that my study, titled “Framing of the 2021 Israel Gaza Conflict: A Content Analysis of Haaretz.com News Coverage” and presented as a Master’s Thesis, has been written without applying to any assistance inconsistent with scientific ethics and traditions. I declare, to the best of my knowledge and belief, that all content and ideas drawn directly or indirectly from external sources are indicated in the text and listed in the list of references.

Zohair Raza
20th June 2023

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS.....	iv
TEXT OF OATH.....	v
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	vi
LIST OF FIGURES	vii
LIST OF TABLES.....	viii
LIST OF IMAGES.....	x
SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS.....	xiii
CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.1. THE CONTEXT OF MEDIATIZATION.....	2
1.2. BASIS OF MEDIATIZATION IN COMMUNICATIVE CONSTRUCTIVISM	3
1.3. FURTHERING THE CONCEPT OF MEDIATIZATION: POLITICAL DISCOURSE CO-RELATION WITH NEWS MEDIA	4
1.4. CONCEPTUALIZATION OF FRAMING.....	6
CHAPTER 2 GLOCALIZATION OF NEWS	8
2.1. GLOBALIZATION AND SYSTEMS OF GLOBAL NEWS COMMUNICATION....	8
CHAPTER 3 STATE, NATION AND, NON-STATE ACTORS.....	12
3.1. PERCIEVED IMAGE OF A NATION STATE	12
3.2. NON-STATE ACTORS AND STATE.....	14
CHAPTER 4 INFORMATION DURING TIMES OF CONFLICT	17
4.1. RALLY AROUND THE FLAG EFFECT	17
4.2. OFFICIAL SOURCE PROBLEM.....	19
4.3. IMAGE WAR IN PALESTINE ISRAEL CONFLICT	20
4.4. THE CASE OF HAARETZ.....	22
CHAPTER 5 METHODOLOGY	24
CHAPTER 6 RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS	29
6.1. ANALYSIS.....	29

6.2. CONCLUSIONS	49
REFERENCES	52
APPENDIX 1 – Content Analysis Measure for Frames	68

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1.1. Percentages of Subcategories	30
Figure 1.2. Does the Story Suggest that some level of government has the ability to alleviate the problem?.....	31
Figure 1.3. Does the story suggest that some level of government is responsible for the issue/problem?.....	33
Figure 1.4. Does the story suggest solution(s) to the problem/issue?	34
Figure 1.5. (1) Does the story suggest that an individual (or group of people in society) is responsible for the issue/problem? (2) Does the story suggest that the problem requires urgent action?	35
Figure 1.6. Does the story employ adjectives or personal vignettes that generate feelings of outrage, empathy, caring, sympathy, or compassion?.....	37
Figure 1.7. (1) Does the story provide a human example or “human face” on the issue? (2) Does the story emphasize how individuals and groups are affected by the issue/problem? (3) Does the story go into the private or personal lives of the actors?	44
Figure 1.8. (1) Does the story reflect disagreement between parties/individuals/groups/countries? (2) Does one party/individual/group/country reproach another?	45
Figure 1.9 (1) Does the story refer to two sides or to more than two sides of the problem or issue? (2) Does the story refer to winners and losers?	46
Figure 2.0. (1) Does the story contain any moral message? (2) Does the story make reference to morality, God, and other religious tenets? (3) Does the story offer specific social prescriptions about how to behave?.....	48
Figure 2.1. (1) Is there a mention of (financial) losses or gains now or in the future? (2) Is there a mention of the costs/degree of expense involved? (3) Is there a reference to (economic) consequences of pursuing or not pursuing a course of action?.....	49

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1.1. Coding Schema	28
---------------------------------------	----

LIST OF IMAGES

- Image 1.1.** “Israeli anti-rocket system intercepts rockets fired from Gaza, today” . Credit: Ohad Zwigenberg..... 38
- Image 1.2.** “Emergency services at the site of a rocket attack in Ramat Gan on Saturday” . Credit: Moti Milrod..... 39
- Image 1.3.** “ A Palestinian man salvages documents and copies of the Koran from the rubble of the Qlebo mosque at the Jabalia refugee camp in the northern Gaza Strip after Israeli air shelling early on Saturday” . Credit: Mohammed Abed / AFP. ... 40
- Image 1.4.** “Fire and smoke rise above buildings in Gaza City after IDF strike, May 2021” . Credit: Anas BABA / AFP..... 41

SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS

ABBREVIATIONS:

IDF Israeli Defense Forces

USA United States of America

UAE United Arab Emirates

AKP Adalet ve Kalkınma Partisi (Justice and Development Party)

CHP Cumhuriyet Halk Partisi (Republican People`s Party)

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

During the often-re-occurring conflicts between Israel and Hamas, Israeli military has a mutually agreed censorship policy with the media (Israel Democracy Institute, 2003). Most of the Hebrew press has a respectful attitude in their coverage of the army, treating claims made by the official spokesperson as facts despite them maybe assertions. This trust in the official source is in an environment when Israeli Army has misled the public on various issues; one incident being the killing of a disabled person in *Tulkarem* or the fact that the Army kept the residents of Northern border in an information blackout, denying any existence of Hezbollah attack tunnels (Sokol, 2018).

However, Haaretz functions differently by generating its own sources for the upkeep of an independent editorial and news stories with information procured from the strip by employing local journalists reporting direct accounts from the territories. However, this proximity to the state officials and high circulation among the political elite and legislators (Korn, 2004) makes *Haaretz* important despite low circulation amongst the Israeli civilians but point of information related to Israel by the world through its online English website; This coupled with headlines like” Why does the world media love to hate Israel?” (Burston, 2009) when the Israeli Defense Forces (IDF) is fighting on the public relations front as well in the context of online global image construction of itself (Tsoref, 2010).

The focus on image construction that sided with the Palestinian sentiments first emerged on the incident of Muhammad Al Durra, in which a child huddled behind his father as they are caught in between the clashes between protestors and IDF broadcasted worldwide. It was an unplanned imagery in which the boy and father became symbols of Palestinian resistance. The incident resulted in an all-time low public image of Israel. The IDF tried to tone down the incident. Contrary to other tabloids, Haaretz refused to use state sources and conducted its own investigation which led to its questioning of the probing methods used by the IDF and criticized the army for reconstructing the event to prove that IDF soldiers did not kill Al-Durra (Yarchi and Ayalon, 2020a).

In this study, the goal is to analyze how Haaretz framed the entire conflict in its coverage of the 11- days of May 2021 with the linkage to Images of Sheikh Jarrah. This is especially important since Palestinians are using image as a weapon against the IDF (Yarchi and Ayalon, 2020b). It uses a deductive analysis of news stories, op-eds, concerned with the conflict using the frames defined by Semetko and Valkenburg (2000b) in the form of a series of questions spread across five identifiable frames, with each frame concerning with aspects of the issue aligned with the Entman (1993a) conceptualization of framing; that is the Identification of a problem, its causes, and possible solutions to alleviate the issue.

The reason for conducting this study is because for the first time, the Israeli Arab citizens took an active part in reacting to the Sheikh Jarrah incident.

1.1 The Context of Mediatization

Firstly, according to Hepp (2012a) the notion of mediation and mediatization are not in opposition of each other (Hepp, 2012b) instead they are complimentary features of communicative action (Knoblauch,2013). Mediation, being a dimension of action (Schutz and Luckmann, 1989) is expanded into two components of social action, that is, immediate and mediated forms of social action (cf. Gebhardt, 2008). The intersection of social action with technology has created a form of social action called interactivity (Rammert, 2012). This penetration of communication technology into face-to-face interaction resulting in the overlap of social orbits (Lundby, 2009). To this, Latour presents the concept of technologies as actors in the same sense as their organic counterparts, the human actors. He further argues that societies are not built upon human actors exclusively, but these societies are the result of relations between several types of actors including objects and technologies, hence allowing for the questioning of the role of objectifications through his actor network theory (Latour 1993a, Latour, 2005b). Through the concept of networks of actors, mediators are introduced as links between local and trans-local. Through this conceptualization of linkage between actors by mediating objects, the primacy of local is challenged and Latour asserts that local is not more real than the mediated interaction (Latour, 1995c).

These mediated interactions are grouped as panoramas, or termed as centers of co-ordination (Suchman, 1993) which are frames and contexts of a certain way in which societies are produced

in a way which supersedes the situation (Latour, 2005d). However, actor network theory entirely ignores the interpretations and or thoughts for such associations or the resulting institutions and neither about the impact of actors on each other and the wider network (Couldry, 2008). Hence, action network theory is indifferent to the meaningful aspects of objects and technologies inherent in the performance of communicative action (Knoblauch, 2013d)

For the reasons of additional aspects necessary for mediatization, the theoretical media extension of actor network theory suggests distinguishing of media representation types. The first type of representation is the interchangeability of methods in such a way that the mediating technologies are not apparent. The second type of representation is the mediation transformed into message (VanLoon, 2008). Thus, mediation and medialization are both features of mediatization which contains both the meaning and the message as interpreted by the mediators. This theorizing of mediatization asserts that media is an extension of actions and the embedded certainty of change in the forms of communication. Hence mediatization is the study of change in the structures of communicative action, in the position of mediatization as a general feature of communicative action (Knoblauch, 2013e).

1.2 Basis of Mediatization in Communicative Constructivism

Communicative constructivism is a further development on the concept of social constructivism due to criticism and challenges inherent in the theory. This shift from social to communicative also has a basis in the empirical research conducted on it. Communicative constructivism was initially started in the German language research but eventual traction within the broader Anglo-Saxon cultures widened the research scope.

Historically, the role of communication in the sphere of social sciences has been at the center of sociology. Communication is at the center of Luhmann`s theory (1984) of autopoietic systems in *Soziale Systeme* (Social system), which asserts that just like in the biological systems, the process of autopoiesis can also be applied to a wide range of non-biological systems. Another important theory of the concept is Habermas`s theory of communicative action. These two theories were responsible for the eventual paradigm shift towards communication (Knoblauch, 1995: Luckmann,1997). Habermas`s (1981) theory of communicative action in particular serves as the basis for the concept of mediatization (Knoblauch, 2013a).

Habermas formulated in his theory of communicative action that the action is directed towards others, immediately refers to something and constructed to express personal meaning (Habermas, 1981). Communicative actions can be challenged by actors in which case others reorientate towards the challenged claim to justify unless supported by power, tradition, or norm which poses a discourse oriented by the logic of language. Although Habermas's focus on language underestimates, if not ignores, the role of non-linguistic forms of communication and neglects the forms of communication originating from the body (Knoblauch, 2013b).

Communicative action, despite being reduced to language, still needs a material carrier such as sound, handwritten letter, or visual representations such as signs, bodily gestures among other physical forms of communication. That the value of a sign does not come from the internal components of the language but from its external environment through concept or material (Saussure, 1959). This means that objectivations are materializations for meaning (Baudrillard, 1968; Lury, 1996) and theoretically bridges communicative constructivism and social constructivism in the sense that the signs are not only objectivized in the structures of signs (i.e., language) but also includes meaning oriented objects of actions such as process and the objectivated product (Berger and Luckmann, 1966).

These differences in degree to power and structure formation also extends to codes and styles of communication termed as functional differentiation (Luhmann, 1996). Communicative forms, with their differing styles and codes embedded in the institutions are integrated through the notion of legitimization which presumes the discourse of these institutions in a society. This difference of codes and styles might also face the inherent problem in this duality since difference in styles and codes may also result in rivalry and the resulting disintegration of the environment (Knoblauch, 2013c). Hence, communicative action should be the starting point for the analysis of mediatization (Krotz, 2001).

1.3 Furthering the Concept of Mediatization: Political Discourse Co-Relation with News Media

The definition of mediatization is scattered into various contexts and only recently does the

scholars have made efforts towards the conceiving of a coherent definition; that is media and a phenomenon of cultural and social process, Hence, mediatization lacked a monolithic definition (Krotz, 2007; Schulz, 2004a).

Mediatization was initially applied to the influence of media in political communication and other aspects of the political realm. However, Hjarvard (2008a) defined mediatization as a process through which key aspects of social and cultural activity assume the form of media (Hjarvard, 2008b). According to Schulz (2004b), mediatization is a concept which has correlation with the changes in communication media. He suggests operationalization of mediatization by means of extension, substitution, amalgamation, and accommodation (Schulz, 2004c). Jansson (2002a) asserts that mediatization of culture is an expansion of media into cultural realm (Jansson, 2002b).

The very first understanding of mediatization came from the Swedish media researcher, Kent Asp (1986a). He asserted that mediatization is a process of political life, that is, as a political system, is greatly influenced by the requirements of mass media and the coverage of politics (Asp, 1986b).

The political conceptualization of the term mediatization, acknowledged by Asp (1986c), is greatly inspired by the Gudmund Hernes's term of 'media-twisted reality'. However, his perspective was broader than just analyzing the relationship between media and political life. This is the reason why he never used the term mediatization. His argument held the stance that media has a broader and fundamental impact of social institutions. He furthers the argument that this influence on social institutions is also present in the relations these social institutions have amongst each other. He also analyzed the media as a redistributor of power amongst these institutions such as schools, businesses public administration, organizations and or parties. In conclusion, he questions how the inner working of institutions and their relationship with other social entities are influenced by the media (Hernes, 1978).

Other scholars, like the conceptualizing by Asp (1986d), delved into media's influence on political life. A series of case studies were conducted on Fernando Collor de Mello's for his 1989 Brazilian elections campaign, Silvio Berlusconi's use of media to aid his power struggle in Italy, and Tony Blair's use of the 'spin' in England. Through these studies, it was demonstrated that media has increasing influence on exercising of political power. In conclusion, mediatized politics is not autonomous in its inner workings and depends on mass media for its core functions and actively being transformed due to the nature of its interaction with the mass media (Mazzoleni & Schulz,

1999).

In a study conducted on Al-Jazeera, Iskander and Nawawy (2004) coins the term of contextual objectivity to illustrate the peculiarity of journalism and presentation as well as journalistic stance of Al-Jazeera, an Arab global broadcaster. They define contextual objectivity as an ongoing tension between the decontextualized news product and the contrived or nuanced perception of the receiver. This is present in all reporting of a conflict by every news outlet across the globe and not just Al-Jazeera. It is ever present in a story and representing of the race for the construction of mediated message (Iskander and El-Nawawy, 2004).

Likewise, the journalism landscape and the dissemination practices are being re-organized by means of technology. This further makes it difficult to contain or control the ideas emanating from sources which are deemed undesirable by governments. Al-Jazeera and many other regional or global news outlets are disseminating images and ideas which might not be considered as likeable by western democracies and their inability to control or censor this contra-flow or reverse flow of media products from these former colonized or disadvantaged countries (Cottle, 2006).

Here, I am linking this contra-flow of influencing variables to the earlier discussed influence of mediatization on politics. This transformation of political thought and practices by mediatization is not omni-flow but a reciprocal process. The phenomenon of rally around the flag effect is the best example for such complimentary nature of mediatization and political communication.

1.4 Conceptualization of Framing

The concept of framing was first introduced by Gregory Bateson (1972a) in which he described psychological frames as a sort of appending set of interactive messages into spatial and temporary bounding (Bateson,1972b). Goffman (1964a) was among the first scholars to have formulated a general concept of framing. He asserts that a schemata of interpretation is employed by an individual for an event in such a way that is primary. Here he describes primary as something not referring to any original interpretation; In other words, it's the organization of an event (Goffman, 1964b).

In news framing, it is described as a narrow framework which restricts the perception of a whole event by means of limiting different realities whilst tending to only one perspective resulting in

the pronouncing of certain aspects of the reality to make them more prominent in the news (Tuchman, 1978). In this approach, framing is defined as a process by which some aspects are made prominent with greater emphasis to define a problem, list its causes, moral judgements are prescribed along with the possible solutions and proposed actions (Entman, 1993b).

One important note here is that some scholars have identified the lack of a heterogenous conceptualization of framing theory. This lack of a centralized conceptualization results in contradiction (McCombs, 2006). However, it is not seen as a weakness by everyone as this diversity in approaches, theoretical models, and origination of understandings from different disciplines is beneficial to the understanding of a concept as complex as framing and the effect of media (D`Angelo, 2002). Likewise, Reese (2007) is also of the opinion that the substance of framing theory is not in its potential of being a unified paradigm but in its ability to bind different methodologies of research; Be it psychological, sociological, academic, or professional research (Reese, 2007b).

This binding of differing approaches can be seen in the fact that media is seen as an institution that only creates and transmits the news frames; That the framing theory is not exclusive to the sender messages but is in both, sender, and receiver (Ardèvol-Abreu, 2015a). Hence, the scientific literature distinguishes between media frames and audience frames (Scheufele, 1999). For media frames, it can be said to start with journalists who are limited by deadlines, routines and or space restrictions decide on which aspects of an event shall make it into the news and which ones shall be omitted or given less importance over the others. The process then continues into the problem identification in the context of important aspects selected by the journalists, its causes, and solution to the identified problem which eventually becomes a frame (Ardèvol-Abreu, 2015b).

CHAPTER 2

GLOCALIZATION OF NEWS

2.1 Globalization and Systems of Global News Communication

Globalization is the amplification of social affairs in such a manner that the intra-local is linked without regards to the spatial so that the localities are affecting each other over great distances (Giddens, 1990). However, some scholars, early in the 1990`s hypothesized a homogeneity of the world because of globalization or usage of homogenous systems, but also because the consumption and consumerism are poised as main tenets of late modern culture (Ritzer, 1996).

According to the above-mentioned view, globalization, to these scholars, is an extension to the hegemony of the west, particularly the American forms of imperialism (Schiller, 1985; Latouche, 1996; Ritzer, 1998). Latouche argues that the base western ideology and culture is being adopted across the different regions. The concepts of race, religion, personal freedom to the way people is interacting with food, entertainment, work patterns and or the choice of architecture is all being convergent towards the pivot of west, or American exemplification (Latouche, 1996).

Ritzer (1996), in his thesis of Mcdonaldization, he states that it was derived from (Ritzer, 1996) Max Weber`s theory of rationality (Kalberg, 1980), Ritzer further elaborates that the homogenization of consumerism is ilk to the principle of fast-food pattern that inevitably erode into other aspects of American society as well as the rest of the world. Others along similar lines of concept, hypothesize that the world is heading towards a mono global culture or the suggested term 'McWorld', a word play of the global fast food restaurant chain. The term is defined as the homogenization of consuming experience linking all forms of entertainment consumption modes into a vast global enterprise (Barber, 1995)

This phenomenon of McDonaldization, according to some scholars, is further expanding in both space, and time. They see this erosion well into social institutions as well as encompassing geographical spaces (Giddens, 1984; Harvey 1989). There are few examples of this homogeneity incurring into other cultural, social, and even military institutions (Albright, 1995: Ritzer, 1996). In the news sector, the success of formats peculiar to USA TODAY, as they were the first ones to

introduce them, has led others to offer similar or exact copy of the formats such as colored weather maps or shorter stories (Prichard, 1987).

However, there is a set of scholars who favor a different angle to the concept of globalization that is more nuanced than those who favor the homogeneity thesis. Giddens (1994), for example, agrees that initially the phenomenon of globalization was governed by the institutions located in the west but with the progression of time, this one-way imperialism is no longer valid even though globalization is still dominated by the western powers. He further asserted that there is no clear direction of globalization (Giddens, 1994). There's the counter argument catering to the concept of hybridization that is the natural mixing of global and the local (Pieterse, 1995). A similar concept originating from the east is called glocalization, a translation of the Japanese term used for the phenomenon presented by Ronald Robertson borrowed from the business context of globalization. Glocalization, in its basic understanding, refers to the marketing of products and services at a global level through the supply of local demands. In this conceptualizing, the local is not subordinated by the global or vice a versa (Robertson, 1995).

Amongst the major scholarship on globalization, there is the assertion that global market and transactional corporations are driving the global context but also making nation states or labor unions as forms of social coherence structures obsolete, which is seen as sign of progress (Ohmae, 1990, 1995). Those scholars, who hold a dystopic view of globalization, argue that globalization is traditional capitalism of economic imperialism using technology to maintain international hierarchies. (Hobsbawm, 1994; Smith, 1997).

The scholarship on globalization and its relationship to communication holds the argument that globalization as a transitional phase has a complex link with communication (Held et al., 1999). Globalization is not only responsible for trans-continental flow of products or capital and people but also the media products amongst many other things across international borders (Appadurai, 1996; Pieterse, 1995; Schiller, 1985; Thussu, 2007a; Tomlinson, 1991). As discussed above, this Janus-faced duality of globalization, according to some, is also present in the newsrooms across the world. The production of foreign news packages is ultimately aimed at domestic news broadcasters specific to the readership across the world (Baden and Tenenboim-Weinblatt, 2017a; Cohen, 2013a).

The few big media conglomerates holding much of the international news arena (Bagdikian, 2004;

Devereux, 2003) are essentially conscious of their *modus-operandi*; these transnational agencies should be one thing for all (Fenby, 1986). However, despite the global approach, these agencies are serving local clients (Baden and Tenenboim-Weinblatt, 2017b; Cohen, 2013b) , hence the product should be a delicate balance between global and local or *glocal*, be it in during the adaptation of the news that was made for global desks into local editorial practices (Baden and Tenenboim-Weinblatt, 2017c; Cohen, 2013c; Cohen, 1996; Cohen and Roeh, 1992; Shoemaker et al., 2012). This is since globalization of news genre in media products are, according to some, flow contra, subaltern and or at times counter flow (Thussu, 2000b). The example here for contra-flow is Al-Jazeera, an International Arab broadcaster with products flowing towards the Western countries and United States of America (Sakr, 2007; Wessler & Adolphsen, 2008).

Journalists often seek news story ideas from other news outlets due to time constraints and other factors (White, 1950). Likewise, Inter-media agenda setting effects have been empirically demonstrated in previous studies such as the in one study, correlation between an international news agenda of a traditional newspaper and three evening time television channels (Golan, 2006). Not only traditional news outlets, but cross platforms of information dissemination have been found to influence the agenda setting between different mediums, such as political blogs (Meraz, 2011). In the analysis of reporting of an earthquake event, it was revealed a link between traditional journalism and the social media in the capacity of mutual influence (Endo, 2013; Russell Neuman, Guggenheim, Mo Jang, & Bae, 2014).

This glocalization translates in newsrooms of international news services in the form of several factors. At times, the local correspondent will be asked to change the caption of a picture by an editor who is based in a different far off geographical location. Consequently, in the same study the AFP photo desk in Israel explains that they use a delicate word play to make the news easily digest by both local and global audiences in the captioning of the photographs. For example, Jerusalem will not be written as the capital of the State of Israel or the word `terrorist` is avoided at all costs in the captioning for photographs (Ilan, 2020).

Here, an important aspect to note is that most of the major news media agencies catering to the global audience use English; News in other languages is also understood through the medium of English media, for example, if something happens in France, news in Bangladesh about this incident will be reproduced from an English source (Pampalone, 2019a).

English is also the preferred language for transnational business engagements. Quoting a survey by Ipsos, a Reuters article stated that the default language of international business is English. The survey included 16,344 individuals from 26 countries. The results showed that 67% of these professionals who engage with nationalities other than their own, use English as their preferred language for interaction. Adding on to the findings, the article states that the workers in three regions, Asia-Pacific, Africa, and the middle east employ English for mutual communication (Michaud, 2012).

An earlier study investigated the phenomenon of English as the default language of the Internet due to internet's genesis in the United States of America. Widespread acceptance of English as a medium of global communication supports the intensification of global social relations suggested by Giddens (1994c), as stated above. English is also the language of global economic institutions such as the World bank since the Washington Consensus is written in English. Moreover, Hollywood has amplified its use in the global celebrity culture. The diplomatic communication between diplomats of various nations is in English (Block, 2004). English is an established lingua-franca of the Internet. It is coded into the fabric of internet as early on as its development by the English-speaking North Americans who did not anticipate at the time that the ASCII character set is not sufficient for other languages of the world (Danet and Herring, 2006).

CHAPTER 3

STATE, NATION, AND NON-STATE ACTORS

3.1 PERCIEVED IMAGE OF A NATION STATE

A state is a settlement of human community that legitimizes the use of physical force within a demarked geographical territory (Weber, 1958). Contrary to the state, a nation is not required to have physical territory for governing of laws and erecting of constitutions (Stiehm, 1984), however a state must have sovereignty over a defined territory (Shain, 1989).

In the Marxist theory of state, a state is a product of society. It is society which originates a state from itself at a certain level of development. This requirement of defining the building block of state comes from the need to have a superpower in the society to further protect the act of and the retention of property ownership. The existence of the concept of property ownership simultaneously produces the opposite of it, that is, the non-ownership of property. The contrast is not complementary and irreconcilable. For such factors, laws are enacted for the safeguard of ownership and the development of mechanisms for it. Eventually, at a certain point the state rises above society and owns non-expandable powers (Marx and Engles, 1989).

Pre-modern states were not defined by the territory enclosing a homogenous boundary of various territories. Pre-modern states were more concerned with the control of people rather than lands they held in its control (Benjamin, 1986a). The citizens of a pre-modern state were not accounted for their linkage to the state but vassal to lord formed the political structure (Tuchman, 1989). However, the modern states encompass the notion of breaking from the political centralization of the past, with no intended continuity to the social and historical past. This act of discontinuity from the past with whatever proceeds from it is defined as achieving independence. Hence, this independence has more to do with the discontinuity from the past rather than the acknowledgment of increased autonomy of internal and external affairs. This means that the modern notion of nation-statehood is about entering into a complex network of international legal systems, political, cultural, and economic structures which affect its external as well as internal factors of social circumstances. This creates the paradox of independence in dependence. This phenomenon is not particular to post-colonial societies but all the nation-states with a membership in the United

Nations; be it a former colonial power, a capitalist society or even a socialist state (Benjamin, 2015).

Some scholars argue that a nation state in its most basic dimension is a consequence of industrialization. This need for a nation has risen by the need to establish an education system that is responsible for training and sorting labor workers capable of managing and operating the industries (Gellner, 1974, 1983; Dore, 1976, 1997a, 1997b).

The variable of globalization in the theories of nation-state are furthering the definition of nation-state beyond the traditional sovereignty. One of the pressing arguments is that globalization is seen as an anti-thesis to the sovereignty of the nation states in the context of socio-economic and political autonomy (Jotia, 2011). Therefore, the question arises of how nation states are perceived in global media and how they themselves frame internal events Infront of the global spectator.

A nation is described as ethnic nationalism or *völkisch*. It is a German term to describe German romanticism and a reaction to the enlightenment movement and the concept of universality originating from the French revolution. This thought process encompasses the *Blut und Boden* or blood and soil concept which adheres to the idea that a race is historically associated, linked, or bound with a certain geographical area which is definite. In this sense, a nation is considered as a birthmark. Individuals are identified with their nationality and people with foreign origins, or the *others*, are seen as a threat to the national identity and common ancestry. Consequently, a nation is entitled to a sovereign state through, paradoxically, historical link to the land and any other group should be either subjugated or expelled from this claimed land (Karlsson, 2009).

A generic search on Google for the word *image* returns About 25,270,000,000 results. On the first page of the returned query, most of the searches are of localized Google business directory assisted and incorporated Google maps. The only link which provides a theoretical understanding of the word is by Wikipedia well below on the page.

A second search specific to Israel with the keyword *Image of Israel* returns about are mostly framed within the tourism context even when the pages listed on the first page are stock image providers. The sole purpose to focus on the first page of Google returned queries is mainly because almost 75% of users do not go beyond the first page (Kagan, n.d.). These searches were originated from Karachi, Pakistan, United States of America, The Kingdom of Netherlands, and Singapore using a virtual private network (VPN). All the queries returned identical results, focusing on the

touristic sights available in Israel.

An image of a nation is the cumulative attributes imagined by a person when the name of the imagined nation arises. This image is three part analytically discernable components which are: Cognitive, affective and action. Each component has different values. For example, the cognitive component is related to what is known, Affective component is linked to feelings about a nation and action component is the actual behavior towards a nation. (Kunczik, 2016a) The cognitive component is the subjective knowledge about a nation held by an individual. The affective component is described as like, dislike, approval or disapproval and the level of hostility towards the said nation by an individual. The action component is a behavioral tendency of a person towards a nation (Scott, 1965). Hence, a nation's image is defined as cognitive representation of a nation in the subjective of a person and what the said person deems true about this nation in his or her mind. The place of political action in the variables of positive or negative assigned to this other nation and the feeling about its future are important factors in these components (Kunczik, 2016b). Here, Kunczik implies that folk learning or science, both are inadequate to shape a nation's image due to the complexity of international system and its workings (Kunczik, 2016c). However, other scholars have a contrasting opinion on the subject. According to this school of thought, image building is a deliberate action on account of government agencies. This perspective suggests that public diplomacy is used by state institutions as a tool of communication targeted at other nations to project a desired image. This projection sometimes is used to even influence the shape of the perception and opinions of the people in the targeted state (Dutta-Bergman, 2006).

3.2 NON-STATE ACTORS AND THE STATE

In this frame of globalized world, non-state actors play a crucial role in local and world politics. The hegemony of states was decentralized until recently, especially after the neo-liberal economic measures. The term non-state actors usually have a negative connotation attached to it. However, organizations like The World Bank, Gazprom, Huawei Technologies and Transparency International, as well as Al-Qaeda are all non-state actors. They all command the international news headlines alongside the states and often influence the decision-making processes of states. However, the widespread spectrum of varieties of these non-state actors, accordingly, influences international affairs in various ways. These numerous types of non-state actors, which may include

but are not limited to, non-governmental organizations, multinational corporations, private militaries, lobbying groups, media outlets, criminal organizations, organized ethnic groups, academic institutions, terrorist groups, social movements etc. All these types of exercise have different forms of power. Some of these non-state actors may work towards the security and stability of a state whilst others might work against it (Wijninga, et al, 2014).

Traditionally, States were coherent and only legitimate actors in world politics (Morgenthau, 1948.), however recently, mostly due to globalization and the advancements in communications technologies, a multi-polar world order resulting in the unpacking of state *modus operandi* (Castells, 1996; Wendt, 1999), there is a trend in last few decades to outsource or privatize some functions of state, which ultimately creates more opportunities for the rise of non-state actors. Likewise, the Westphalian model of state existing in a multi-pivoted anarchical world has also been radically reshaped in parts of the world, such as the EU as an international institution that influences state matters. This resulted in the declined influence of state, benefiting the non-state actors (Wijninga, et al, 2014).

In the context of armed conflict, the essence of it is unchanged and probably will remain unchanged (Dubik, 2013) according to the argument put forward by Clausewitz, however, the character of a conflict has been gradually changing (Clausewitz, 1943). According to William S. Lind, states around the world are fighting non-state actors (Lind, 2004). For example, Hamas, Hezbollah, Revolutionary armed forces of Colombia are all fighting against or being a parallel to the state itself, and everywhere, the states are facing heavy losses (Levitt, 2015). The Americans, for example, were never defeated in any conflict until Vietnam war, and the USSR against the Afghan Mujahideen (Hammes, 2016). The common denominator here is an organized military against a band of non-state armed militia, making any armed conflict between them an asymmetrical affair where one party, the state backed military, has technological, logistical, tactical, and organizational advantage but is bound to International Humanitarian laws such as the Geneva Convention. The other, the non-state actor, might not have the above said advantage but it does not subscribe to any international law of conflict or any other law. The only law applicable to the non-state actor are the domestic laws. However, the nature of conflict for them is the denial of such domestic laws. This subscription to Article 1 of Protocol 2 of International Humanitarian law or other laws restricts the amount of violence which can be used against the non-state adversaries. This restriction is disadvantageous to the state and balances the power between the asymmetrical

adversaries (Paulus and Vashakmadze, 2009).

CHAPTER 4

INFORMATION DURING THE TIMES OF CONFLICT

4.1 RALLY AROUND THE FLAG EFFECT

Rally around the flag effect is defined by a favorable majority opinion towards the political leadership in times of national crises. The crises may take shape in the form of various natural or man-made calamities such as the recent pandemic, military conflict with another nation, terrorist attacks and other forms of events which are perceived as threatening to the national sovereignty (Dinesen and Jæger 2013; Hetherington and Nelson 2003; Mueller 1970a). However, this effect is usually short-lived as it is rare for the political leadership to sustain the high popular opinions after the crises has subsided or have been dealt with effectively (Kernell 1978; Mueller 1973; Woods 2011).

For example, according to Karcioğlu et al. (2020), the most substantial global crisis of the century so far has been the Covid-19 pandemic of 2020. It did not only affect the global health infrastructure and threatened life expectancy of adult human population but also affected various aspects of our world, such as economic, social, and political (Karcioğlu et al., 2020). Therefore, research has also been conducted on political communication and how the framing of political discord was mannered during such global events of crisis (Melek & Iseri, 2021), especially when populism was experiencing mass approvals just before the world was hit with the pandemic and even during the entire course of it well into 2021 (Mounk, 2021).

The research conducted by Melek and Iseri (2021), was peculiar in the sense that it also studied media's role as an extension to elite messages during the pandemic crisis in Türkiye. In Türkiye, the crisis did not bring any rally effect, but instead political discord was deepened due to differences in organizing and designing the pandemic specific protocols (Melek and Iseri (2021), between the ruling pro-Islamist *Justice and Development Party* (AKP) and the main opposition, secular social democrat *Republican People's Party* (CHP) (Fox, 2020). The research concluded that mainstream news outlets furthered the political divide by broadcasting frames in favored political affiliations (Melek and Iseri, 2021).

The causality of the above-mentioned absence of rally effect is due to the nuances explored by

Johansson, Hopmann, and Shehata (2021). According to them, the reasons for the decline in the initial and sudden spikes in approval rates is mostly because of the decrease in issue saliency. In their study titled, "*When the rally-around-the-flag effect disappears, or: When the COVID-19 pandemic becomes "normalized"*", they studied the reasons behind declining support and reemergence of ideological debates during the covid-19 crisis management by the Swedish government. They hypothesized that both increase in support, and decline exists in phases. The decline, however, is specific when the crisis is tabulated on ideological planes due to the saliency levels of the issue other than the perceptions around crisis management being the initial driver for the decline outside the ideological debates (Johansson, Hopmann, & Shehata, 2021).

There are multi-dimensional views concerning the rally around the flag effect. One of them is influenced by the social identity theory that is, the triggering of support through national affiliation during a crisis. This usually renders support for national symbols of the group such as the president or head of that nation (Tajfel, 1982). For example, in the context of foreign policy, diversionary war hypothesis asserts that leaders may use the rally round the flag effect to their advantage. According to the hypothesis, a leader can or may invoke rally effect to distract the public from a troubling domestic issue on which the leader is dealing with unfavored public opinion, harsh criticism, or even critically low approval ratings. In practice, a leader may engage in aggressive foreign policy or even military conflicts to make more chances of remaining in power (Levy, 1989).

The second dimension focuses on the threat itself and supports the increase in security in an uncertain situation (Doty et al. 1991). A third dimension focuses on human emotions as the basis for rally around the flag effect, primarily around anger and anxiety as potential triggers (Lambert et al, 2011).

My focus, however, is on the political variable of the effect. According to this perspective, the political elite plays an integral role in the creation of this dimension of the effect. A study conducted by Baker and Oneal (2001a) on approximately 200 military disputes concluded that the magnitude of the rally effect depended on elite messages (Baker and Oneal, 2001b). To analyze it in general terms, the consistency of elite messages tilts the public opinion towards the message (Zaller and R, 1992). Here, an elite message refers to the arguments around a social issue and the influence that the leading elite individuals, groups, and institutions have over shaping public

opinion. Not only public opinion, but previous research demonstrates how social and political elite also influence the policy evaluation through the dissemination of their point of view and actions reported in a peculiar manner by the news media (Aspersen, Shah, Watts, Faber, & Fan, 1998; Sniderman et al., 1993; Watts, Domke, Shah, & Fan, 1999; Zaller, 1992).

4.2 THE OFFICIAL SOURCE PROBLEM

Social control has been demonstrated to have a correlation with the increase in deviancy (Young, 1971). Media definitions of reality are not perceived in isolation but as simultaneously influencing and influenced by reality defining state institutions such as police, judicial system, interest groups and the polity of society (Cohen, 1972a). An analytical study into the process of the development of moral panic and street crime emphasized the relation with the media in generating public anxiety and the subsequent legitimization of law-and-order policing. This also points to the relationship between media and other reality defining institutions as they collaborate in the process of signification and the definitions presented by the media and the frame of references supplied by state representing individuals as well as public figures compliment and justify each other (Hall, 1978). This reality construction is proficient in groups which readily accept such constructed narratives and rally behind even violent measures to relieve their anxieties about a particular perceived social problem (signorielli, 1990). These convictions resulting from constructed reality come from the belief that primary sources are the best definers due to the proximity of these primary sources to the problem and its causes. Moreover, journalists rely on the primary sources for information about the scenario, which is linked with the, for example, criminal justice agencies. These official interpretations then draw a parameter within which all future debates take place (Hall, 1978).

A study conducted of the Vietnam conflict found that journalists never questioned the official sources or looked for evidence in their reportage of the conflict. They accepted the official interpretations as baseline reality without critically analyzing the information. This uncritical acceptance of the official source lasted only until the Tet offensive when the political and military elite was divided in their viewpoints of the war and severe rifts became apparent in the power structures of the US (Hallin, 1986). Similarly, during the Falkland military conflict, the press identification with the official sources tended to be in line with the military narrative due to the

information hegemony of the army about the conflict (Glasgow University Media Group, 1995; Morrison and Tumber, 1988).

During the first intifada, some of the major Israeli newspapers systematically ignored the distinction between Palestinian casualties during armed conflict with those that were of unarmed civilians. In this study, it was revealed that most of the casualties were defined in the frame of armed conflict about the Palestinians. However, most of the Palestinian casualties were of those who did not participate in any violence whatsoever. The phrase “killed in clashes” to frame Palestinian deaths and the use of emphasis in which armed Palestinians were killed gave justification for the use of military action as a legitimate means to oppress the conflict even when most deaths were of Palestinian civilians (Korn, 2004).

Thus, it is observed that, even when terrorists are placed on the media limelight, the reports regarding these individuals or organizations rely upon the official sources to amplify the produced meaning and the replication of state patronized language in otherizing the armed groups with labels as ‘terrorists’ (Paletz and Schmid, 1992; Schlesinger, 1991a; Schlesinger et al., 1983). The portrayal of terrorism in isolation then takes on the meaning of initiating force and the state as a necessary response. This isolating of the act of terrorism without including the historical or socio-political background which will help in making sense of the motivations behind the violent acts portrays it as a senseless irrational behavior. This results in the legitimizing of social control and extra-legal and or excessive state response (Schlesinger, 1991b).

4.3 IMAGE WAR IN PALESTINE-ISRAEL CONFLICT

Conflicts in the information sphere are different from the ones fought on ground (Tovy, 2015). These conflicts have vague borders, and the frontline is where viewers can get information from about the conflict, hence, the political goals of a conflict are achieved through the media coverage (Ayalon et al., 2016).

Such types of conflicts have multiple theatres such as the military, the diplomatic, the legal and the media fronts. This change in the character of a conflict has a major contributor: the coverage of media regarding a conflict and its influence on the behavior of the actors which changes the above-mentioned fronts as well. This change in conduct is due to the image it creates of the actors

involved in said conflict in the perspective of the viewers, determining which side will have its goals completed and or which side prevails (Friedman, 2007a). Hence, a major part of such a conflict is to put forward the narrative each side is trying to promote (Freedman, 2013b).

Previous studies have found similarities between the messages promoted by both – state actors and non-state actors. Both types of actors perceive themselves as victims and put responsibility for starting the conflict on the other side while offering their solution, which will lead to a desired outcome, to end the conflict (Yarchi, 2016). This pattern of problem, cause and solution is like a definition of framing (Entman, 1993c).

A previous study by Yarchi and Ayalon (2020c), presented an example of the narrative which Israel and Hamas are trying to promote to further their reputation in front of the audience. The Israeli narrative emphasizes on self-defense. According to them, they are the victims of this conflict since Palestinian leadership as well as terror groups use their citizens as human shields to undermine the Israeli response which is simply about defending Israeli citizens. This justification of self-defense is used even when the initiator of the conflict is the State of Israel. Israel repeatedly states its desire for peace and take measures towards the improving the lives of Palestinians in hopes of ending the cycle of violence but at the same time stresses on its right to self-defense and protecting its citizens at all costs. In this sense, Israel is presenting its narrative as self-defense against Palestinian terrorism and links it to the global war against terror organizations. This rhetoric of fear of terror and national identity is in line with the immigration waves across the world, hence relatable with a wider audience.

Hamas consider themselves as victims and Israel as an occupying force that frequently harass the Palestinian population. Hamas blames Israeli leadership for this conflict as well as its citizens due to Israel`s mandatory military service. According to Hamas, it is seeking revenge for killing innocent Palestinians through military force, reversing the Israeli narrative that it is the Israelis who are the aggressors and any attack by the Hamas is a response to the Israeli violence. They legitimize this counter violence using the right to self-rule and yearning for independence from an occupation. Israeli blockade of Gaza strip where citizens are not allowed to enter Israel or leave for Egypt, even after living in crippling poverty, enables Hamas to put forward the image of Gaza as a prison. These narrative hopes to provoke the emotions of empathy and the public tendency to identify with the weaker victim whilst keeping the emphasis on Israel`s violence and images of

settlers harassing or using violence against the Palestinians (Yarchi and Ayalon, 2020d). However, Hamas is the third richest ‘terror’ organization in the world according to Forbes, with an annual income of 700 million dollars (Zehorai, 2018). Countries other than, United States of America (USA), European Union (EU), Japan, Israel, and Canada, do not classify Hamas as a terror group (Team, 2021).

The Palestinian narrative, not included in the above-mentioned study, want a two-state resolution and are willing to live with Israel as neighbors (Wion, 2021), is against the octogenarian decree style rule of al-Fatah (Buttu, 2016). According to a poll in 2021, 53% of the Palestinians in a scientific survey conducted by Palestinian Center for Policy and Survey Research, believed that Hamas is the most deserving to represent and lead the people of Palestine. However, according to the head pollster, Khalil Shikaki, this is majorly a rally effect and usually fades away within three to six months after a conflict has taken place and Hamas has failed to deliver on its promises (Krauss, 2021).

The Palestinians have recently taken account of the concept of weaponizing the image as they make strategies to counter the Israeli military actions. While Palestinians are using Imagefare to achieve their political objectives, Israel is focused of the warfare and the military-oriented strategies to counter the Palestinians alongside the Gazan border area. This is because Israel perceives the conflict as a security issue and military threat, undermining the image variable of the conflict. In recent times, during the Israel-Palestine conflict, the international media and public opinion tends to side with the Palestinians and perceive it as human suffering, since the Palestinian narrative invokes compassion. However, Israel was restricted in its use of images to counter the Palestinian narrative which is going to influence Israel on the international arena since the Imagefare used by the Palestinians is going to affect Israel’s global image in the long-term. This can be observed in a decision by European Union in November 2019 which legalize the marking of Israeli products produced in the Israeli settlements (Yarchi and Ayalon, 2020e).

4.4 THE CASE OF HAARETZ

Within Israel and in other parts of the world, Haaretz is both admired and loathed for its op-eds. Many within Israel believe that Haaretz provide points of argument against Israel to her critics. In effect, Haaretz is mostly critical of Israeli policies; It is not a representative of the dominant public

opinion as its mostly to the opposing side of the popular sentiments (Rosner, 2017). Haaretz has a minority readership within Israel, however, over one million viewers count on its websites, both for Hebrew and English. Moreover, Haaretz is believed to have an influence within the state governing corridors (Beckerman, 2005). In effect, despite the low circulation, in contrast to the other major Israeli news outlets, it is still considered to be a quality newspaper and more than once, it's been noted to have high influence on the military, economic and political elite of the country due to the high journalistic standards upheld by the newspaper. (Caspi and Limor, 1999)

Despite Haaretz's infame within broader Israeli public, a network graph analysis by Gilad Lotan (2018) concluded that Haaretz relates to the high number of nodes with both clusters of pro-Israeli and pro-Palestinian nodes. According to the network graph analysis, Haaretz, containing the highest points of betweenness centrality, is believed to have the capacity to bridge the biases and political polarities of the opposing groups. These clusters are, however, not entirely made-up of Palestinians or Israelis but also contain sub-groups such as American Zionists, pro-Palestinian activist groups, media outlets, such as BBC world which tends to favor the Palestinian narrative, etc. (Lotan, 2018).

Haaretz, despite its leaning towards ideological left, also publishes articles of writers or adds news by its reporters who have a centrist point of view on the Palestinian-Israeli conflict. It should not mean that the leftist point of view on the conflict is somewhat inferior or less reliable to the centrist opinions but the fact that, rarely, Haaretz's factual accuracy, analyses and news reports have been refuted (Slater, 2007).

However, critics of Haaretz argue that this once prestigious newspaper has lost its journalistic standards due to several factors, one significant factor being the radicalization of its politics for attracting more internet traffic (Tadmor, 2013). For example, often, the choice of words by Haaretz have caused controversies, sometimes on international level such as in 2018, US Ambassador Tom Nides was involved in a Twitter feud with Haaretz over an op-ed criticizing his support for the Israeli settlements (Ravid, 2018). Another, criticism against Haaretz have been that in its pursuit of Anti-Israelism, Haaretz op-eds often commit antisemitism (JTA, 2016).

CHAPTER 5

METHODOLOGY

The study conducted quantitative content analysis measure for frames defined by Semetko and Valkenburg (2000c), used in the coverage of the 2021 Israel-Gaza conflict by Haaretz in its op-ed and news stories, starting from May 9th 2021 when the far-right dance of flags event was planned to place, up until the May 24th 2021 when the official ceasefire was announced; In total 120 articles were analyzed. The conflict which started due to the court`s decision to evict Palestinians families from the homes in Sheikh Jarrah neighborhood of east Jerusalem which sparked a widespread protest by Israeli civil rights groups and Israeli Arabs. These events provided the opportunity to analyze the news coverage of Haaretz and the frames used on their website. The analysis was specific to the conflict but also included news stories and opinion articles which mentioned the conflict but only if the articles were present on the first page of google.

The data for analysis was collected using the google search engine; keywords followed by targeted date of article publication. The articles collected were from the first page of google search results only since the research on behavior shows that few people go beyond the first page of returned results on google and many marketeers of content strive to achieve a place on the first page. Every article was converted into a downloadable PDF format using a Firefox add-on which allows for html to pdf conversion and download. The search method used in the search bar used a string of keyword Haaretz, followed by, date, month, year. For example, “Haaretz+ 8 may+2021”. This string returned the most relevant articles published by Haaretz which were then crawled by google robots and listed on the first page of its search results. The data was solely collected due to the volatile nature of websites where content may be retracted without any trace of it but just a no-follow dead link.

The pre-defined frames, formulated by Semetko and Valkenburg(2000d), consisted of a series of 20 questions which were coded as yes and no; yes meant 1 and no means 0. The questions are used to identify one of five frames: human interest, conflict, morality, attribution of responsibility, and

economic consequences.

Frame Title	Frame Description	Sample Examples
Attribution of responsibility	<p>This frame contained five questions and majorly contained attributes from Entman`s (1993d) understanding of a news frame. The first question asked if the story is suggesting government ability to alleviate a problem on non-certain level. The second question asked if the story suggest if the government is responsible for the problem or the issue. Third question is concerned with the solution of the observed problem. Fourth question asked to identify any suggestions made regarding the responsibility of a group or individual or people in society for the problem. The final question was about the urgency or action required to solve the problem.</p>	<p>“Escalations in Jerusalem in recent days, and subsequent rocket and incendiary balloon attacks from the Gaza Strip have sparked tensions in the bloc for change. The joint List criticized Lapid for a tweet with regard to the recent clashes: “Anyone who wants to hurt us will know that he will pay a heavy price.”</p>
Human interest frame	<p>Human interest contains five questions. The first question is concerned with if the story contains a human example or a `human face` compared to those stories which keep the telling to numbers and figures. The second question is concerned with the employing of adjectives to render feelings of empathy, caring, sympathy or compassion from the</p>	<p>Yara, 21, also from Umm al-Fahm, says that “what’s happening in Jerusalem is happening not only to its inhabitants,” emphasizing that Arab citizens of Israel struggle so that Arabs, throughout Israel, can exercise their right to remain on their lands.</p>

	<p>reader. The third question looks for any emphasis used in the story for affected individuals and groups by the issue/problem. The fourth question look for detailed sketch of private or personal lives of the actors. The last question looks for visual information that might generate feelings for outrage, empathy, sympathy, or compassion.</p>	
<p>Conflict frame</p>	<p>The conflict frame contains just four questions in total. The first question asks if the story reflect any disagreement between parties, individuals, countries or groups. The second question concerns with which group, individual or country reproach the other. The third question is whether the story refer to two sides or more than two sides of the problem or issue and the final question is to identify any winners or losers engaged in the issue.</p>	<p>“The relationship, however, between East Jerusalem Palestinians and Arab citizens of Israel, is complex. On the one hand, Arab citizens of Israel mediate between East Jerusalem residents and Israeli authorities, as most of them hold top positions in the eastern part of the Israeli capital – lawyers, school principals and government agencies officials. On the other hand, East Jerusalem residents harbor resentment toward the well-off Arab citizens of Israel, who they say have forgotten their Jerusalem brethren who suffer under the Israeli occupation.”</p>

<p>Morality frame</p>	<p>Morality frame is basically concerned with the ethical, moral and religious markers in a story. It contains only three questions. The first one is to identify a presence of a moral message of sorts in the story. The second question asks if the story makes any reference to morality, God or religious tenets. The third question is about the social prescriptions of behaviour.</p>	<p>Twenty people from Lod were also admitted to Shamir Medical Center, including a heavily pregnant woman with a head injury. She gave birth successfully but she remains in an intensive care unit in a serious condition.</p>
<p>Economic frame</p>	<p>Economic frame also has three questions in total. The first question is about identifying the presence of financial losses or gains in present or in foreseeable future. The second question is about whether the story mentions any costs or degree of expenses involved in the issue. The last question looks for any reference to economic consequences of pursuing or not pursuing a course of action regarding the issue.</p>	<p>Prior to the event, dozens of right-wing activists marched in the city and attacked a number of Arab-owned businesses. The rioters smashed glass windows, threw objects, and chanted racist slogans.</p>

Coding Schema Table 1. Adapted from the codebook developed by Semetko and Valkenburg (2000e)

A total of 120 articles were analyzed published from 9th of May till the announcement of an Egyptian brokered cease-fire in the early hours of 21st May, however, the news of the cease fire

was updated in the live-updates news article published on Friday 20th May 2021. The calculation method used by the authors of this codebook, Semetko and Valkenburg (2000f), was principal component analysis with a varimax rotation. However, principal component analysis is best used for data samples which are larger than 300 articles in size to produce replicable component loadings with reliability of correlation coefficients. To cope with this, percentages were calculated for each frame variable, pronouncing the components to analyze the data in a detailed manner.

CHAPTER 6

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

6.1. ANALYSIS

Haaretz perceived this conflict mostly as a non-religious one since it framed *Attribution to Responsibility* 31% despite most of the conflict was centered around the *Haram Al-Shareef* and the activities of Ramadan, linkages to *Dance of Flags*, a right-wing demonstration to commemorate the unification of Jerusalem, and its proximity to the *Haram* were prominent in which the reportage was critical of Jerusalem Police Department.

The focus in *Haaretz* reporting was to point out the unwillingness of the government to alleviate the problem or it being the responsible party for the conflict. Here, the term government also included *Hamas* for being the sole administrative authority in *Gaza*. The consequences *Haaretz* stated of this conflict were humanitarian. Although, *Hamas* was criticized less times for its role in the conflict, nor *Hamas* was blamed for interfering in Israeli internal matters. However, despite reporting of humanitarian crisis, personal accounts were not frequently included into the reportage.

Haaretz also did not mostly report personal lives but focused on the broader aspects of the conflict. Economic frame was reported the least times, alongside morality frame.

Highest presence amongst the sub-categories, 9.0%, was the question in Conflict Frame *Does the story reflect disagreement between parties/individuals/groups/countries?* This sub-category was mostly present in articles dealing with either the riots between Israeli-Jewish and Israeli Arabs/Leftists. This was most often followed by news dealing with reportage of rocket attacks from Gaza into Central Israeli towns and the reciprocal attacks by IDF into Gazan civilian buildings. Mentioning of civilian casualties was most emphasized rather than the military progress of IDF, however, the political capital gained by *Hamas* through the conflict was often discussed as a reflection to the criticism dotted on former Israeli prime minister or linkages to the mismanagement of events in Sheikh Jarrah neighborhood in east Jerusalem or raiding of Al-Aqsa compound by the police.

Figure 1.1. *Percentages of Subcategories.*

During the first two days of the conflict, Haaretz frequently gave analysis on the ability of government to play a role in alleviating the issue, with two spikes of 14.5% till 12th of May but as the days progressed the newspaper begin to include *Individuals responsible for the issue* variable in its assessment in addition to government`s unwillingness despite having the resources or the ability to engage in a manner that would put an end to the entire situation. It was done by establishing linkages between the two subcategories of the *Responsibility* frame. For example, in article 27 published on 11th May, the Haaretz editorial posits that the lack of strategic depth on part of the government despite having the ability to alleviate the issue or avoid it altogether only if the government paid a heed to intelligence officials, army and police recommendations. This linkage pattern persisted throughout the first four days in which the news organization acknowledges government ability to alleviate the problem and its failure to do so due to poor decision making, or even accused the government of deliberately forcing the state into a war with *Hamas*. The criticism, however, was minimized due to the urgency of other events appearing, such as the increase in the success ratio rockets going past the Iron Dome interceptors and landing on civilian settlements. However, on 16th May, there`s another 14.5% identical spike in the *ability* subcategory (Figure 2) with the linkage and minimal reporting on violence across the Israeli cities between Arabs/Leftists and the right-wing Jews. This reflects best in article no.83, of which an excerpt is

needed to better illustrate the linkage. In the article, it reads:

“Most Israelis are unaware of the reason underlying the extreme brazenness of Hamas, which is spearheading rocket attacks taking a toll on our lives like never before. The reason is that the leaders of this terror organization know that Israel under Benjamin Netanyahu isn’t only reluctant to end Hamas’ hold in the Gaza Strip, it wants to preserve it.” Writes Dmitry Shumsky in his opinion column.

This illustrates that, on average, the rally-around-flag effect was minimal, and the government was heavily criticized for its lack of interest in alleviating the problem. These spikes were prominent across the two sub-categories, however, rarely the newspaper used a tone in which *Hamas* was criticized for interfering in internal matter of Israel. Moreover, *Hamas*, do not see the events in and around *Al-Aqsa* compound as Israel’s internal troubles, as mentioned in article No.40 which reads:

“Hamas, by the way, never gave up on its role in East Jerusalem or on the struggle for the Temple Mount, and by its own estimation crossed no red line. Israel is the one who defined this attack as a red line, despite the fact that Jerusalem has already been targeted by rockets in past conflicts.” States Zvi Bar’el analyzing the situation on 12th May 2021.

Figure 1.2. *Does the story suggest that some level of government has the ability to alleviate the problem?*

This is a particularly important point to highlight since this is an asymmetrical warfare between the state of Israel which abides to many international laws and the other being largely a non-state actor.

Zvi Bar'el goes further and quotes the Egyptian Foreign Minister *Sameh Shoukry* on the issue, who stated that the conversations with Israel did not yield the desired results. Such analysis was seen as a linkage between the government's ability to alleviate a problem with the subcategory *Does the story suggest that some level of government is responsible for the issue/problem?* (Figure 3)

“Not only have Cairo's efforts not borne fruit, they have been politely but firmly rejected. According to sources in Egypt who were quoted in Arab media outlets, Israel's coldness led Egypt to support the escalation, encouraging Hamas to continue its attacks from the Gaza Strip while instructing the Egyptian media not to criticize the group.” Zvi Bar'el 12th May 2021.

Moreover, on May 19th (Figure 3), Haaretz published the most criticism on both warring parties, 19.7%. Most harsh amongst it was criticism on the government and the Israeli state for ill-treatment of the Palestinians and on *Hamas* for leveraging Palestinian lives for her military and political goals. Not only did the articles criticize the government but also the Israeli military for its selective approach of engagement. In her opinion piece, Amira Hass, an Israeli-Jewish journalist, reflects on the chain of events in coherence towards the last days of the conflict. This was coded for the sub-category of *Does the story suggest that some level of government is responsible for the issue/problem?* In the frame of *Attribution of Responsibility* In article no.106 she states:

“Israelis who run around in a panic when the warning sirens go off, abandoned towels on the beach in Tel Aviv, the closing of Ben-Gurion Airport – these scenes arouse feelings of schadenfreude among all Palestinians who live in the shadow of the intimidating and arrogant military and police power of Israel.

The army that the Hamas movement has built, its perseverance despite the blockade and the assassinations, its military capability of surprise and ability to put millions of Israelis in a state of fear, have brought it into the big leagues that regional and global politics must take into consideration.

The Hamas regime, which excelled at building an army, did not invest in building shelters for

civilians. It is dependent on aid from international organizations, led by UNRWA, to provide a safety net and the most minimal, feeble provisions to residents at this time. Hamas also knows very well that most of the burden of the reconstruction (slow and nerve wracking) will be borne by foreign countries and the hated government in Ramallah.” Writes Amira Hass on 19th May 2021.

Despite holding *Hamas* responsible for being the biggest reason of humanitarian crises it creates for the Gazan civilians nor denying the fact that Hamas use civilians as a leverage for its own military or political goals, she is emphasizing more on Israel for being the sole reason for all the tragedy and conflict due to the fact that Israel is a proper state with a functioning government accepted by most of the world nations including middle-eastern and/or Muslim majority countries, such as Egypt, *Türkiye* and United Arab Emirate (UAE).

Figure 1.3. *Does the story suggest that some level of government is responsible for the issue/problem?*

In article no.94 of the May 18th issue, the decision to redirect the flag march route to Jaffa gate to avoid any skirmishes between the far-right Zionist groups and the Arabs living on the traditional route of the flag march, the Damascus gate, and the Muslim Quarter. However, the article still suggests that the situation could have been avoided if Jerusalem police department was not unprofessional in its conduct. As illustrated in above (Figure 4) Suggestions were 5.2% higher by the end of the conflict but during the initial days of the conflict also the newspaper prescribed suggestions with a 12.3% being the highest amongst the first three days. For example, in article no.2, in the form of emphasizing the importance of protesting for the right to worship and including

inter-faith solidarity extended to the Palestinians in Sheikh Jarrah by Israeli- Arabs and even Israeli *Druze* community which historically avoided getting involved in Arab matters and certainly not in Palestinian issues. This pattern remains consistent during the entire course of the conflict, sometimes included with emphasizing measures taken against the rioters in mixed Israeli cities, in particular the city of Lod which has seen the worst communal riots in an otherwise peaceful co-existence amongst the Jewish and Arab residents.

Figure 1.4. Does the story suggest solution(s) to the problem/issue?

The subcategories of *Does the story suggest that an individual (or group of people in society) is responsible for the issue/problem?* And *Does the story suggest that the problem requires urgent action?* observes mentioning of responsible groups or individuals in society and if the issue caused by these individuals require an urgent solution to be deployed. These variables were recorded in the presence of articles either holding the state civilian groups such as the police department or individuals such as the prime minister or the minister of defense Benny Gants but seldom did the newspaper questioned the protests by Jerusalemites. However, the Arab-citizens of Lod were heavily criticized and reason behind the spikes from 9th till 16th May (Figure 5) for their involvement in riots and property destruction while sparsely pointing blame on far-right Jewish groups. During the middle days and the last day's presence of the frame subcategories was related to Hamas rocket fires as the frequency of rocket attacks increased during these periods.

As observed, the responsibility variable was addressed more frequently than urgency of action. For example, all the major spikes, 7.5% on 9th of May, 6.8% on 12th of May and 6.1% on 14th of

May, belong to the question of *Does the story suggest that an individual (or group of people in society) is responsible for the issue/problem?*

There was less emphasis on the urgency of solution than the reporting of the events. Nonetheless, this variable was effectively present throughout the timeline of the conflict only to be diminished at the announcement of ceasefire. Most of the presence for this frame consisted of reportage regarding diplomatic efforts made by various countries, including, France, United States of America (USA) and Egypt, as well as calls for immediate restraint on Israeli part by Turkish president, *Recep Tayyip Erdogan*. For example, article no.90, published on 18th of May, reports about the German call for an Israel-Gaza ceasefire and a divide of opinion amongst the EU states. The article was relayed by Haaretz from Reuters news agency and has a presence of *Does the story suggest that the problem requires urgent action?* In the *Attribution of Responsibility*. It states that: *“Today, I will lobby for a better humanitarian supply in Gaza,” Maas said, pledging 40 million euros (\$48.86 million) to ramp up humanitarian aid for civilians in Gaza.*

The EU is Israel's biggest trade partner and a big aid donor to the Palestinians but has been reluctant to use such leverage or discuss possible economic sanctions on Israel's government.”
 May 18th, 2021.

Figure 1.5. (1) *Does the story suggest that an individual (or group of people in society) is responsible for the issue/problem?* (2) *Does the story suggest that the problem requires urgent*

action?

The question of whether *Does the story employ adjectives or personal vignettes that generate feelings of outrage, empathy, caring, sympathy, or compassion?* And *Does the story contain visual information that might generate feelings of outrage, empathy, caring, sympathy, or compassion?* Had uneven spike ratio. Haaretz employed more personal vignettes, shown in blue bars in figure 6, than visual information, represented in blue. However, the second question was still present in substance with two spikes of 7.9% and 8.7%, identical to the spikes of first question. The first question was mostly found present in news reportage regarding civilian casualties. For example, in article no.76 the report headline talks about the conferring of Israeli army to the Israeli government to allow for more attacks on Gaza. However, IDF oppose the idea over the concern of further civilian casualties in the strip. The report further delves into the situation in Gaza and the humanitarian crises due to the conflict faced by the Palestinian civilians. The article in the presence of the subcategory of *Does the story employ adjectives or personal vignettes that generate feelings of outrage, empathy, caring, sympathy, or compassion?* In the frame of *Human Interest*, states:

“Senior officers told Haaretz that offensive actions are providing ever diminishing returns, especially after Thursday night’s massive attack in which a Hamas tunnel network in northern Gaza was destroyed. In the assault, Israeli planes dropped 450 tons of bombs. The IDF is worried that further attacks will lead to civilian casualties.

Israeli airstrikes last week killed dozens of people, including many women and children. The toppling of an apartment building that housed the offices of several media outlets and Hamas has stirred international criticism, even though Israel warned the occupants to leave.” Writes Amos Harel on 16th of May 2021.

Figure 1.6. *Does the story employ adjectives or personal vignettes that generate feelings of outrage, empathy, caring, sympathy, or compassion?*

The question *Does the story contain visual information that might generate feelings of outrage, empathy, caring, sympathy, or compassion?* Was usually present in the form of visuals of rocket barrages against the backdrop of a night sky and the subsequent intercepting missiles deployed by the Iron Dome (see Image 1). The next widely used visuals were of wreckages of Israeli homes hit by a bypassing Hamas rocket (see Image 2) or collapsed houses after an IDF airstrike (see Image 3 and 4). These images always had someone in the frame except for the rocket vs missile motif which had a more symbolic meaning to it. Moreover, Haaretz also published the images of flashes or fire clouds due to the Israeli weapons but in lesser frequency than the first three motifs. These pictures were coded in the sub-category of *Does the story contain visual information that might generate feelings of outrage, empathy, caring, sympathy, or compassion?* In the frame of *Human Interest*.

Image 1.1. *“Israeli anti-rocket system intercepts rockets fired from Gaza, today”*. Credit: Ohad Zwigenberg

Image 1.2. “Emergency services at the site of a rocket attack in Ramat Gan on Saturday”. Credit: Moti Milrod

Image 1.3. *“A Palestinian man salvages documents and copies of the Koran from the rubble of the Qlebo mosque at the Jabalia refugee camp in the northern Gaza Strip after Israeli air shelling early on Saturday”*. Credit: Mohammed Abed / AFP

Image 1.4. “*Fire and smoke rise above buildings in Gaza City after IDF strike, May 2021*”. Credit: Anas BABA / AFP

In the *human-interest* frame, seldom did the newspaper go into the personal lives of the affected group. As shown above (see Figure 7) the question *Does the story emphasize how individuals and groups are affected by the issue/problem?*, shown in green, have second highest percentage in all three subcategories, however, the question *Does the story provide a human example or “human face” on the issue?* That has the highest presence is not significant with 42.1% for the second question and 43.7% score for the human face subcategory.

The significant rise in question *Does the story provide a human example or “human face” on the issue?* and *Does the story emphasize how individuals and groups are affected by the issue/problem?* is due to the higher ratio of opinion and analysis articles in which the authors are going in-depth of the situation focusing on the humanitarian variable. To better illustrate, the following is a list of headlines of selected articles which have a pronounced human face or details about the groups/individuals affected by the issue. These were coded in *Human interest frame*.

Analysis | Gaza Lives Erased: Israel Is Wiping Out Entire Palestinian Families on Purpose

The numerous incidents of killing entire families in Israeli bombings in Gaza – Parents and children, babies, grandparents, siblings – attest that these were not mistakes. The bombings follow a decision from higher up, backed by the approval of military jurists – Amira Hass May 19, 2021

Attacks on Israeli Journalists on the Rise After Years of Right-wing 'Delegitimization'

Some high-profile Israeli correspondents were provided security details in response to violent threats - Sam Sokol May 19, 2021

Opinion | Hamas Has Entered the Big Leagues

The Hamas regime, which excelled at building an army, did not invest in building shelters for civilians from Israeli strikes. It entered, with its eyes wide open, a new campaign in which its ability to defend its citizens was nil. Amira Hass May 19, 2021

“Analysis | Israel Has Abandoned All Its Citizens, Not Just Its Arab Ones Much of the bitterness and violence that erupted in ‘mixed’ Arab Jewish cities last week was about resentment over privilege. But it was also about poverty and inequality, and augurs ill for any potential one state solution.” Anshel Pfeffer May. 19, 2021

General Strike Highlights Israel's Dependency on Palestinian Workers The Israel Builders Association said the strike over the situation in Gaza, Jerusalem and in mixed cities across Israel paralyzed building sites, causing estimated losses of nearly \$40 million

'Abandon Israel': Network of Fake Accounts Tries to Demoralize Israelis During Gaza War Watchdog and social analytics firms discover drive to push out disinformation on Twitter, Instagram during the latest confrontation between Israel and Hamas, and suspect Tehran is behind the effort." Omer Benjakob and Refaella Goichman May. 19, 2021

No Longer Silent, Gulf Arab Citizens Are Outraged at Israel as Gaza Conflict Rages Analysts say the conflict will also set back Israeli efforts to secure more normalization deals with other Arab states, like Saudi Arabia The Associated Press May. 19, 2021

Israeli Airstrike Cripples Gaza's Only COVID Center Vaccination of 3,000 people a day grinds down; 17 hospitals, clinics reportedly damaged by Israeli strikes Jack Khoury May. 19, 2021

Opinion | The Real Cause of Violence Is the Arabs Abed L. Azab May. 19, 2021

Arab General Strike in Israel and West Bank Widely Observed 'The assault on Palestinians in Jerusalem, in Sheikh Jarrah and at the Al-Aqsa Mosque' and 'the assault on the Arab public in general and in mixed cities in particular,' prompted the strike, the Higher Arab Monitoring Committee said Fadi Amun, Deiaa Haj Yahia, Nir Hasson, Jack Khoury, Hagar Shezaf and Yanal Jbareen May. 19, 2021

Figure 1.7. (1) *Does the story provide a human example or “human face” on the issue?* (2) *Does the story emphasize how individuals and groups are affected by the issue/problem?* (3) *Does the story go into the private or personal lives of the actors?*

In the *conflict* frame, most of the presence for the first two questions were due to the mentioning of Hamas and Israel, or the fighting units of the two. As illustrated (see Figure 8) the most presence amongst the two is of the subcategory spikes, 15.2% of 7.6% each, which asks *Does the story reflect disagreement between parties/individuals/groups/countries?*. This is coupled with the second question is *if the countries or the groups reproach each other* which has the second highest spike of 6.4%.

Figure 1.8. (1) *Does the story reflect disagreement between parties/individuals/groups/countries?*
 (2) *Does one party/individual/group/country reproach another?*

Due to the lower presence of the question “*Does the story refer to winners and losers?*” (See Figure 9) the blue bar which represents the “*Does the story refer to two sides or to more than two sides of the problem or issue?*” takes up most of the spikes on the graph but also makes a more coherent link with the first two items of the *conflict* frame. The two sides mentioned in the articles were on the 9th of May regarding the clashes between the police and the protestors at the Al-Aqsa compound. The second spike is on the 16th of May when the newspaper started publishing opinions about the increasing death toll in Gaza and heavily criticized the government for a lack of exit plan from the conflict. The reportage on this day in the context of the *conflict* frame sub-category, was mostly about the gains and losses, both military and civilian, on either side. The opinions and analysis were based on the incoming news for which Haaretz relied upon its own sources as well as international news agencies to provide the information from Gaza strip.

In article no.76, coded in the *conflict frame*, notes that most of the arrests took place in response to the rioting, most notably in the city of Lod, were suspects from the Arab community. However, the report further adds that:

“Sources at the State Prosecutor’s Office said they planned to press more charges “soon,” including against Jewish Israelis involved in anti-Arab violence.” Bar Peleg and Netael Bandel
 May. 16, 2021

However, the report then delves into the narrative of the prosecutors and pen the progress or problems they are facing in trying to get everyone involved in the rioting to the court regardless of the ethnic or religious affiliation. The report adds:

“The police have been preparing for another week of unrest across the country, but officials are complaining that a lack of quality intelligence, especially on Jewish suspects, has prevented the police from halting escalations in time.

Police officials fear two scenarios: either a clash between Jews and Arabs that kills another civilian, such as the shooting of Moussa Hassouna in the central city of Lod, or an Arab Israeli being shot dead by the police.”

Yet, the report, despite balancing all accounts, adds quotation marks over some words from the official sources.

Figure 1.9. (1) *Does the story refer to two sides or to more than two sides of the problem or issue?*

(2) *Does the story refer to winners and losers?*

The *morality* frame was predominantly present in the form of mentioning the Al-Aqsa compound which is a central point for the Ramadan festivities but also tenets in the Judaism. In the reports, the newspaper has also prescribed a moral behavior for dealing with such sites which hold religious sanctity. However, one opinion piece, for example, article no.9 by Rogel Alpher published on May 9th, 2021, delves into the politico-religious aspects of the temple mount, mentions it in the context of right-wing religious Zionism. This excerpt was coded in the *morality frame*. The author states that:

“Jerusalem Day marks the occasion when Israel conquered the Temple Mount. Not liberated, conquered. If you read opinion pieces in the right-wing Makor Rishon, Israel Hayom or Arutz 7, you’ll learn that the Temple Mount is the most sacred place in the world to Jews.

That’s a lie. It’s a fact that I’m a Jew, and the Temple Mount is not sacred to me. The truth – and sometimes it’s worth declaring a simple truth, it’s the best cure for false propaganda – is that the Temple Mount is not sacred to millions of Israelis.” Rogel Alpher May. 9, 2021

In this process of refuting the popular belief of Temple mount/*Haram Al-Shareef*, as sacred to the three Abrahamic religions, the article makes the presence of various variables (see Figure 10) present or given in the second question of *Morality* frame, that is: *Does the story make reference to morality, God, and other religious tenets?* (Represented with red colored bar)

Figure 2.0. (1) *Does the story contain any moral message?* (2) *Does the story make reference to morality, God, and other religious tenets?* (3) *Does the story offer specific social prescriptions about how to behave?*

Despite it being an affair of armed conflict, which involves loss of resources to be engaged, fewer number of articles were concerned with the cost of war. In fact, the presence of *economic* frame was mostly because of the reporting of property damage due to the rioting in Israeli cities or the communal strikes by the Arab Labor Unions. That is the reason why all the spikes are during the first few days of the conflict (see Figure 11) when rioting was on the rise and human death toll was neither confirmed nor was there any ability to confirm the accuracy of the first information.

Figure 2.1. (1) *Is there a mention of (financial) losses or gains now or in the future?* (2) *Is there a mention of the costs/degree of expense involved?* (3) *Is there a reference to (economic) consequences of pursuing or not pursuing a course of action?*

6.2. CONCLUSIONS

Action is directed towards the other which can be challenged by those actors who are being acted upon (Knoblauch, 2013). By conducting independent investigations and employing reporters from the conflicted zone, just to bypass the official sources, Haaretz.com demonstrates the notion of increased descent, when the social control is present (Young,1971b), amongst the Israeli news landscape.

This attribute to look beyond the official discourse, by reality defining state institutions such as the police, polity, judicial system etc (Cohen,1972b), especially when Haaretz.com is presenting the reportage for international audiences, puts it at odds with the IDF and the state of Israel when both are trying to fight a war of images with the Palestinians to tilt public opinion towards their narrative instead of the Palestinian story (Yarchi and Ayalon, 2020f).

Further complicating the relationship with the state, usage the technology as an actor, or as Latour (1993b, 2005c) presents technology as a counter part to the organic forms, human beings (Latour, 1993c, 2005d), Haaretz.com acts as a pivot point for the sort of international audiences trying to get authentic news about Israel due to Haaretz reputation as a newspaper which is consciously independent in its editorial practices (Caspi and Limor, 1999b).

The aim of this study was to observe the leftist/Israeli Arab narrative through an Israeli newspaper's global audience platform's framework, Haaretz.com. This was especially important because for the first time Israel's left wing and Arab residents were directly involved in the confrontations, something that was rare or non-existent (Hasson & Khamaisi, 2021) till this point when Haram Al-Shareef confrontations were taking place. No quantitative research on such a specific subject has been found by the author of this paper.

The research reveals that Haaretz was not biased towards one narrative or the other but had a, mostly, balanced viewpoint during the conflict. Although it mostly criticized IDF and the Israeli government, Haaretz also criticized Hamas for its use of Palestinians as human shield against Israeli airstrikes; In one instance, Haaretz also highlighted IDF's hesitance of increased airstrikes due to the concerns over higher civilian casualties. However, one thing to note here is that Haaretz's criticism of Hamas was somewhat muted or underwritten when compared to its criticism of Israeli government. Haaretz reporting is also important in the context of Image fare when the Palestinian narrative is usually being sympathized significantly more than the Israeli narrative, especially when Hamas's human rights abuse is of equal footing with Israel's treatment of Palestinian civilians. This notion, as discussed earlier, makes this conflict asymmetrical for both sides of the conflict; For Hamas, it's the status as a non-state actor faced with a proper state with substantial resources for a conflict and for Israel it's the status of a proper state which puts certain limitation, i.e., the international laws and human rights, in her methodology of designing the offensive or defensive strategies against Hamas, especially when Israel is subjected to more international public scrutiny over its actions against Palestinians. And in that context, its reporting serves as a pivot to understand factual reports beyond the social media sentiments. This is also important because the global news product is refitted for the local context to increase the appeal and relevancy for readership of the applying news outlet (Ilan, 2019b).

There isn't much qualitative research present on the 2021 conflict in context of Media reporting. The only other research conducted was on the media reporting of the conflict was a critical discourse analysis of British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC) and New York Times, in which the results revealed that both news outlets were reporting more about Israel's justifications and

interests in contrast to the Palestinian narrative and rights (Amer, 2022). No research was ever conducted on how an Israeli newspaper on this conflict was reporting the conflict, especially using firsthand reportage by employing journalists from the Gaza strip. This reveals that it is fairly a new subject for researchers.

This study, unlike an earlier study by Imtiaz, Khan, Lyu, and Luo (2022) in which they mined Twitter data to account for the public opinion, refrained from acknowledging the comments section of the website articles.

However, this study was limited to analyzing just one Israeli news outlet when other news outlets such as the Times of Israel and Jerusalem Post also has English websites for global audiences, serving different viewpoints. Future research may take this into account and conduct a comparative analysis on the subject which is important since it allows for a broader understanding of Israeli media landscape during this conflict since the global audience usually relies upon the English sources to get information from non-Anglo world (Pampalone, 2020b).

REFERENCES

- Albright, M. (1995). INSIDE JOB: Fast-food Chains Serve a Captive Audience
<https://www.tampabay.com/archive/1995/01/15/inside-job-fast-food-chains-serve-a-captive-audience/>
- Amer, M. M. A. (2022). “BBC and New York Times’ Coverage of the May 2021 Israeli Onslaught on Gaza: A Critical Discourse Analysis.” *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 12(5), 1. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijel.v12n5p1>
- Appadurai, A. (1998). Modernity at large: cultural dimensions of globalization. *International Migration Review*, 32(4), 1073. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2547675>
- Ardèvol-Abreu, A. (2015a). *Framing theory in communication research. Origins, development and current situation in Spain*. <https://doi.org/10.4185/rlcs-2015-1053en>
- Ardèvol-Abreu, A. (2015b). *Framing theory in communication research. Origins, development and current situation in Spain*. <https://doi.org/10.4185/rlcs-2015-1053en>
- Asp, K. (1986a). *Mäktiga massmedier: Studier i politisk opinionsbildning [Powerful mass media: studies in political opinion-formation]*. Stockholm: Akademilitteratur.
- Asp, K. (1986b). *Mäktiga massmedier: Studier i politisk opinionsbildning [Powerful mass media: studies in political opinion-formation]*. Stockholm: Akademilitteratur.
- Asp, K. (1986c). *Mäktiga massmedier: Studier i politisk opinionsbildning [Powerful mass media: studies in political opinion-formation]*. Stockholm: Akademilitteratur.
- Asp, K. (1986d). *Mäktiga massmedier: Studier i politisk opinionsbildning [Powerful mass media: studies in political opinion-formation]*. Stockholm: Akademilitteratur.
- Ayalon, A., Popovich, E., & Yarchi, M. (2016). From Warfare to Imagefare: How States Should Manage Asymmetric Conflicts With Extensive Media Coverage. *Terrorism and Political Violence*, 28(2), 254–273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09546553.2014.897622>
- Bateson, G. (1972). *Steps to an ecology of mind: Collected essays in anthropology, psychology, evolution and epistemology*. San Francisco, CA: Chandler.
- Barber, B. (1995). *Jihad vs. McWorld*. New York: Random House.

- Baudrillard, J. (1968). *Le syst`eme des objets*. Paris, France: Gallimard.
- Baden, C., & Tenenboim-Weinblatt, K. (2017a). Convergent news? A longitudinal, study of similarity and dissimilarity in the domestic and global coverage of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. *Journal of Communication* 67(1), 1–25.
- Baden, C., & Tenenboim-Weinblatt, K. (2017b). Convergent news? A longitudinal, study of similarity and dissimilarity in the domestic and global coverage of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. *Journal of Communication* 67(1), 1–25.
- Baden, C., & Tenenboim-Weinblatt, K. (2017c). Convergent news? A longitudinal, study of similarity and dissimilarity in the domestic and global coverage of the Israeli-Palestinian conflict. *Journal of Communication* 67(1), 1–25.
- Baker, W. M., & Oneal, J. R. (2001a). Patriotism or Opinion Leadership? *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 45(5), 661–687. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022002701045005006>
- Baker, W. M., & Oneal, J. R. (2001a). Patriotism or Opinion Leadership? *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 45(5), 661–687. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0022002701045005006>
- Benjamin, R. (1986). The Angevin Empire. *History Today* 36 (2), 17–22.
- Benjamin, G. (2015). The unseen presence: a theory of the nation-state and its mystifications. *Inter-Asia Cultural Studies*, 16(4), 548–585. DOI:10.1080/14649373.2015.1103071
- Bergmann, J., & Luckmann, T. (Eds.) (1999). *Kommunikative Konstruktion von Moral, Bd.1: Struktur und Dynamik der Formen moralischer Kommunikation*. Opladen, Germany: Westdeutscher Verlag.
- Block, D. (2004, January 1). Globalization, Transnational Communication and the Internet. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net>
- Blumler, J., & Kavanagh, D. (1999). *The third age of political communication: Influences and features*. Online: *Political Communication*, 16, 209–230.
- Bourdieu, P. (1980). *Le sens pratique*. Paris, France: Editions Minuit.
- Burston, B. (2009, March 23). Why does the world media love to hate Israel? - Haaretz Com. *Haaretz.com*. Retrieved from <https://www.haaretz.com>
- Buttu, D. (2016, December 12). The Palestinian leadership that doesn't represent us. Retrieved from <https://www.aljazeera.com>
- Castells, M. (2009). *Power in the network society*. In M. Castells (Ed.), *Communication power* (pp. 10–53). New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- Caspi, D., & Limor, Y. (1999). *The In/outsiders: The Media in Israel*. Hampton Press (NJ).

- Castells, M. (1996). *The Information Age: Economy, Society and Culture*. Cambridge, MA: Blackwell.
- Christmann, G. (in press). *Towards a communicative construction of spaces*. London, England: Routledge.
- Clausewitz, K. (1943). *On War*, trans. Jolles O. J. Matthijs. New York: Random House.
- Cohen, A.A. (2013a). *Foreign News on Television: Where in the World Is the Global Village?* New York: Peter Lang.
- Cohen, A.A. (2013b). *Foreign News on Television: Where in the World Is the Global Village?* New York: Peter Lang.
- Cohen, A.A. (2013c). *Foreign News on Television: Where in the World Is the Global Village?* New York: Peter Lang.
- Cohen, A. A. (1996). Global newsrooms, local audiences : a study of the Eurovision news exchange. In *Libbey eBooks*. <https://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA30390509>
- Cottle, S. (2006b, January 1). *Mediatized Conflict: Developments in Media and Conflict Studies*. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net>
- Cooley, C. H. (1909). *The significance of communication*. In *Social Organization* (pp. 61–65). New York, NY: Charles Scribner’s Sons.
- Coleman, J. S. (1990). *Foundations of social theory*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Couldry, N. (2008a). Mediatization or mediation? Alternative understandings of the emergent space of digital storytelling. *Online: New media & society*, 10 (3), pp. 373-391. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/1461444808089414>
- Couldry, N. (2008b). *Form and power in an age of continuous spectacle*. In D. Hesmondhalgh, & J. Toynbee (Eds.), *The media and social theory* (pp. 161–176). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Danet, B., & Herring, S. C. (2006). Introduction: The Multilingual Internet. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 9(1), 0. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1083-6101.2003.tb00354.x>
- Dore, R. (1976a). *The Diploma Disease: Education, Qualification and Development*.

London : Allen and Unwin.

- Dore, R. (1997b). The Argument of the Diploma Disease: a summary. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 4(1), 23–32.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594970040102>
- Dore, R. (1997c). Reflections on the Diploma Disease Twenty Years Later. *Assessment in Education: Principles, Policy & Practice*, 4(1), 189–206.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0969594970040113>
- Doty, R. L., Peterson, B. E., & Winter, D. (1991). Threat and authoritarianism in the United States, 1978–1987. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 61(4), 629–640.
<https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.61.4.629>
- Dubik, J. (2013). Learning from a Decade-Plus of War. Institute for the Study of War. Retrieved from <https://understandingwar.org>.
- Dutta-Bergman, M. J. (2006). U.S. Public Diplomacy in the Middle East. *Journal of Communication Inquiry*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0196859905285286>
- Endo, K. (2013). Social journalism in the inter-media society: Results from the social survey on the great East Japan earthquake and the Fukushima nuclear power plant disaster. *Journal of Contemporary East Asia*, 12(2), 5–17.
- Entman, R. M. (1993a). Framing: Toward Clarification of a Fractured Paradigm. *Journal of Communication*, 43(4), 51–58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.1993.tb01304.x>
- Entman, R. M. (1993b). Framing: Toward Clarification of a Fractured Paradigm. *Journal of Communication*, 43(4), 51–58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.1993.tb01304.x>
- Entman, R. M. (1993c). Framing: Toward Clarification of a Fractured Paradigm. *Journal of Communication*, 43(4), 51–58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.1993.tb01304.x>
- Entman, R. M. (1993d). Framing: Toward Clarification of a Fractured Paradigm. *Journal of Communication*, 43(4), 51–58. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.1993.tb01304.x>
- Fenby, J. (1986). *The International News Services*. New York: Schocken Books.
- Friedman, T. (2020, May 1). In Turkey, Erdogan Is Playing Politics with Coronavirus Relief. *Foreign Policy*. Retrieved from <https://foreignpolicy.com>
- Freedman, L. (2013). *Strategy: A History*. Oxford University Press.
- Friedman, T. L. (2007). *The World is Flat: a Brief History of the Twenty-First Century*. Picador USA.

- Gebhardt, J. (2008). *Telecommunications in everyday life. A social phenomenological analysis of interpersonal media communication*. Wiesbaden, Germany: VS.
- Gellner, E. (1975). *Legitimation of Belief*. Cambridge University Press.
- Gellner, E. (1983). *Nations and Nationalism*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Giddens, A. (1984). *The Constitution of Society: Outline of the Theory of Structuration*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Giddens A. (1990). *The Consequences of Modernity*. Stanford University Press: Stanford, CT.
- Giddens, A. (1994). Risk, trust, reflexivity. In U. Beck, A. Giddens and S. Lash, *Reflexive Modernization: Politics, Tradition and Aesthetic in the Modern Social Order*: Stanford. Stanford University Press.
- Glasgow University Media Group (1995). The Falklands War: making good news. In G. Philo (Ed.), *Glasgow Media Group Reader, Vol. 2*, (76–101). London: Routledge.
- Goffman, E. (1964a). The Neglected Situation. *American Anthropologist*, 66(6_PART2), 133–136. https://doi.org/10.1525/aa.1964.66.suppl_3.02a00090
- Goffman, E. (1964b). The Neglected Situation. *American Anthropologist*, 66(6_PART2), 133–136. https://doi.org/10.1525/aa.1964.66.suppl_3.02a00090
- Goffman, E. (1981). *Forms of talk*. London, England: Blackwell.
- Golan, G. J. (2006). INTER-MEDIA AGENDA SETTING AND GLOBAL NEWS COVERAGE. *Journalism Studies*, 7(2), 323–333. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14616700500533643>
- Gumperz, J., & Hymes, D. (Eds.) (1972). *Directions in sociolinguistics: The ethnography of communication*. New York: Holt, Rinehart, and Winston.
- Habermas, J. (1981). Theorie des kommunikativen Handelns. *Suhrkamp eBooks*. Retrieved from <https://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA0613873X>
- Hacking, I. (1999). *The social construction of what?* Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Hammes, T. X. (2006). *The Sling and the Stone: On War in the 21st Century*. Zenith Press.
- Harvey, D (1989). *The Condition of Postmodernity: An Inquiry into the Origins of Cultural Change*. Oxford: Blackwell.

- Hall, S. (1978). *Policing the Crisis: Mugging, the State, and Law and Order*. MacMillan.
- Harvey, D. (1989). *The Condition of Post-modernity: An Inquiry into the Origins of Cultural Change*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Hallin, D.C. (1986). *The Uncensored War: The Media and Vietnam*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Hartmann, M., & Hepp, A. (2010b). *Die Mediatisierung der Alltagswelt (Medien • Kultur • Kommunikation) (German Edition)* (2010th ed.). VS Verlag für Sozialwissenschaften.
- Hasson, N., & Khamaisi, Y. J. F. (2021, May 9). Arab citizens of Israel show unprecedented involvement in Jerusalem protests - Israel News. *Haaretz.com*. Retrieved from <https://www.haaretz.com>
- Hepp, & F. Krotz (Eds.). *Mediatisierte Welten* (pp. 27–58). Wiesbaden, Germany: VS.
- Hepp, A. (2012a). Mediatization and the ‘molding force’ of the media. *Communications*, 37(1), 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1515/commun-2012-0001>
- Hepp, A. (2012b). *Cultures of mediatization*. Cambridge, MA: Polity Press.
- Heath, C., Knoblauch, H., & Luff, P. (2000). Technology and social interaction: the emergence of ‘workplace studies.’ *British Journal of Sociology*, 51(2), 299–320. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00071310050030190>
- Held, D., McGrew, A., Goldblatt, D., & Perraton, J. (1999). *Global Transformations: Politics, Economics and Culture*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Hernes, G. (1978). Det mediavridde samfunn [The media-twisted society]. In G. Hernes (Ed.), *Forhandling sekonomi og blandningsadministrasjon*. Bergen: Universitets forlaget.
- Hjarvard, S. (2008a). The Mediatization of Society: A theory of the media as agents of social and cultural change. *Nordicom Review* 29 (2008) 2, pp. 105 – 134
orientation. In K. Nyíri (Ed.), *A sense of place: The global and the local in mobile communication* (pp. 159–168). Wien, Germany: Passagen.
- Hjarvard, S. (2008b). The Mediatization of Society: A theory of the media as agents of social and cultural change. *Nordicom Review* 29 (2008) 2, pp. 105 – 134
orientation. In K. Nyíri (Ed.), *A sense of place: The global and the local in mobile communication* (pp. 159–168). Wien, Germany: Passagen.
- Hobsbawm, E. (1994). *The Age of Extremes*. London: Abacus.

- Hoflich, J. R. (2005). *A certain sense of place: Mobile communication and local*
- Intiaz, A., Khan, D., Lyu, H., & Luo, J. (2022). Taking sides: Public Opinion over the Israel-Palestine Conflict in 2021. *arXiv (Cornell University)*.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.2201.05961>
- Ilan, J. (2020, June 1). Glocalization and international news-photo production: News images from Israel made for global news markets. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1464884919847802>
- Iskander, A.L., & El-Nawawy, M. (2004). Al-Jazeera and War Coverage in Iraq: The Media's Quest for Contextual Objectivity. pp. 315- 23 In S. Allen and B. Zelizer (Ed.), *Reporting War*. London, Routledge. McChesney, R.W (2003) 'Corporate Media, Global Capitalism', pp. 27-39 in S. Cottle (ed.) *Media Organization and Production*, London: Sage.
- Jansson, A. (2002a). The Mediatization of Consumption: Towards an analytical framework of image culture. *Journal of Consumer Culture*, 2(1), 5–31.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/146954050200200101>
- Jansson, A. (2002a). The Mediatization of Consumption: Towards an analytical framework of image culture. *Journal of Consumer Culture*, 2(1), 5–31.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/146954050200200101>
- Jotia, L. (2011). *Globalization and the Nation-State: Sovereignty and State Welfare in Jeopardy*. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED528356.pdf>.
- Keller, R. (2005). *Analysing Discourse. An Approach From the Sociology of Knowledge*. *Historical Social Research*, 6(3), 223–242. <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-6.3.19>
- Karlsson, I. (2009). What is a Nation?. Retrieved from <https://www.files.ethz.ch>
- Kagan, M. (2016, October 20). 100 Awesome Marketing Stats, Charts, & Graphs [Data]. Retrieved from <https://blog.hubspot.com/blog/tabid>
- Karcioglu, O., Yüksel, A., Ateş, C., Er, A. B., Esendagli, D., Gülhan, P. Y., Kokturk, N. (2020). Covid-19: The Biggest Threat of the 21st Century: In Respectful Memory of the Warriors All Over the World. *Turkish Thoracic Journal*, 21(6), 409–418. <https://doi.org/10.5152/turkthoracj.2020.20069>
- Kendon, A. (2004). *Gesture: Visible action as utterance*. Cambridge, MA: Cambridge University Press.
- Kernell, S. (1978). Explaining Presidential Popularity: How Ad Hoc Theorizing, Misplaced Emphasis, and Insufficient Care in Measuring One's Variables Refuted Common Sense and Led Conventional Wisdom Down the Path of Anomalies. *American Political Science Review*, 72(2), 506–522. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1954107>
- Knoblauch, H. (1995). *Kommunikationskultur. Die kommunikative Konstruktion*

- kultureller Kontexte. Berlin, Germany: De Gruyter.
- Knoblauch, H. (2001). *Communication, contexts and culture. A communicative constructivist approach to intercultural communication*. In A. di Luzio, S. Günthner, & F. Orletti (Eds.), *Culture in communication: Analyses of intercultural situations* (pp. 3–33). Amsterdam, the Netherlands: John Benjamins.
- Knoblauch, H. (2013a). Communicative Constructivism and Mediatization. *Communication Theory*, 23(3), 297–315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/comt.12018>
- Knoblauch, H. (2013b). Communicative Constructivism and Mediatization. *Communication Theory*, 23(3), 297–315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/comt.12018>
- Knoblauch, H. (2013c). Communicative Constructivism and Mediatization. *Communication Theory*, 23(3), 297–315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/comt.12018>
- Knoblauch, H. (2013d). Communicative Constructivism and Mediatization. *Communication Theory*, 23(3), 297–315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/comt.12018>
- Knoblauch, H. (2013e). Communicative Constructivism and Mediatization. *Communication Theory*, 23(3), 297–315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/comt.12018>
- Knoblauch, H., & Schnettler, B. (Eds.) (2006). *Video analysis: Methodology and methods. Qualitative audiovisual data analysis in sociology*. Frankfurt, Germany: Peter Lang.
- Knoblauch, H. (2010). *Wissenssoziologie*. Konstanz, Germany: Universitätsverlag Konstanz.
- Knoblauch, H. (2011). *Relativism, meaning and the new sociology of knowledge*. In R. Schantz, & M. Seidel (Eds.), *The problem of relativism in the sociology of (scientific) knowledge* (pp. 131–156). Frankfurt, Germany: Ontos.
- Knoblauch, H. (2012). *Powerpoint and the communication culture of knowledge society*. New York, NY: Cambridge University Press.
- Knorr Cetina, K. (2001). Post social relations: Theorizing sociality in a post social environment. In G. Ritzer, & B. Smart (Eds.), *Handbook of social theory* (pp. 520–537). London, England: Sage.
- Knorr Cetina, K. (2012). Skopische Medien. In F. Krotz, & A. Hepp (Eds.), *Mediatisierte Welten. Forschungsfelder und Beschreibungsansätze* (pp. 167–196). Wiesbaden, Germany: VS.
- Korn, A. (2004). Reporting Palestinian casualties in the Israeli press: the case of Haaretz and the Intifada. *Journalism Studies*, 5(2), 247–262. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1461670042000211212>
- Krotz, F. (2001). *Die Mediatisierung sozialen Handelns*. Wiesbaden, Germany: VS.

- Krotz, F. (2012). Von der Entdeckung der Zentralperspektive zur Augmented Reality. In A. Kunczik, M. (2016). Images of Nations and International Public Relations. Routledge.
- Krauss, J. (2021, June 15). Poll finds dramatic rise in Palestinian support for Hamas. Retrieved from <https://apnews.com>
- Krotz, F., & Hepp, A. (Eds.) (2012). *Mediatisierte Welten*. Wiesbaden, Germany: VS.
- Krotz, F. (2007). *Mediatisierung: Fallstudien zum Wandel von Kommunikation*. Springer-Verlag.
- Lambert, A. J., Schott, J. M., & Scherer, L. D. (2011). Threat, Politics, and Attitudes. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 20(6), 343–348. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963721411422060>
- Latouche, S. (1996). *The Westernizing of the World*. Cambridge: Polity Press
- Latour, B. (1993). *We have never been modern*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
- Latour, B. (2005). *Reassembling the social: An introduction to actor-network-theory*. Oxford, England: Oxford University Press.
- Latour, B., & Hermant, E. (1998). *Paris ville invisible*. Paris, France: La D'ecouverte.
- Leroi-Gourhan, A. (1964–1965). *Le Geste et la Parole, 1. Technique et Langage, 2. La M'emoire et les Rythmes*. Paris, France: Albin Michel.
- Levitt, M. (2015). *Hezbollah: The Global Footprint of Lebanon's Party of God*. Washington DC: Georgetown University Press.
- L'evi-Strauss, C. (1955). *Les tristes tropiques*. Paris, France: Pion.
- Livingstone, S. (2009). On the mediation of everything. *Journal of Communication*, 59(1), 1–18.
- Lind, W. S. (2004). Understanding Fourth Generation War. *Military Review*, 84(5), 12. Retrieved from <https://www.hsdl.org/?abstract&did=482203>
- Lotan, G. (2018, April 1). Israel, Gaza, War & Data - i ♥ data - Medium. Retrieved from <https://medium.com/i-data/israel-gaza-war-data-a54969aeb23e>
- Luckmann, T. (1985). The analysis of communicative genres. In B. F. Nell, R. Singh, & W. M. Venter (Eds.), *Focus on quality: Selected proceedings of a conference on qualitative research methodology in the social sciences* (pp. 48–61). Durban, South Africa: Institute for Social and Economic Research.

- Luckmann, T. (1997). *Le paradigme communicationnel dans la "nouvelle" Sociologie de la Connaissance*. *Sociétés: Revue des Sciences Humaines et Sociales*, 55, 89–98.
- Luhmann, N. (1996). *Social systems*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Lundby, K. (2009). Introduction: 'Mediatization' as key. In L. Lundby (Ed.), *Mediatization: Concept, changes, consequences* (pp. 3–18). New York, NY: Lang.
- Lury, C. (1996). *Consumer culture*. London, England: Polity.
- Marx, K., & Engels, F. (1989). *Karl Marx, Frederick Engels: Collected Works*. International Publishing Company Incorporated.
- Marten, P. (2014). State and Non-State Actors: Beyond The Dichotomy. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net>
- Mazzoleni, G., & Schulz, W. (1999). "Mediatization" of Politics: A Challenge for Democracy? *Political Communication*, 16(3), 247–261.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/105846099198613>
- McCombs, M. (2006). Estableciendo la agenda. El impacto de los medios en la opinión pública y en el conocimiento [Setting the agenda the impact of the media on public opinion and knowledge]. Barcelona: Paidós.
- Melek, G. & İşeri, E. (2021). When a Polarized Media System Meets a Pandemic: Framing the Political Discord over COVID-19 Aid Campaigns in Turkey. In P. Van Aelst & Jay G. Blumler (Eds), *Political Communication in the Time of Coronavirus*. (pp.136-154). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Meraz, S. (2011). Using Time Series Analysis to Measure Intermedia Agenda-Setting Influence in Traditional Media and Political Blog Networks. *Journalism & Mass Communication Quarterly*, 88(1), 176–194.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/107769901108800110>
- Mead, G. H. (1934). *Mind, self, and society*. Chicago, IL: University of Chicago Press.
- Meyrowitz, J. (1994). Medium theory. In D. Crowley, & D. Mitchell (Eds.), *Communication theory today* (pp. 50–77). London, England: Polity.
- Michaud, C. (2012, May 16). *English the preferred language for world business: poll*. U.S. Retrieved from <https://www.reuters.com>
- Mounk, Y. (2021, April 26). How Populism Has Proven Lethal in This Pandemic. Council on Foreign Relations. Retrieved from <https://www.cfr.org>
- Morrison, D. E., & Tumber, H. (1988). *Journalists at War: The Dynamics of News Reporting During the Falklands Conflict*. Sage Publications.

- Mueller, J. E. (1973). *War, Presidents, and Public Opinion*. New York: Wiley.
- Mullen, M. G. (2009, August 28). Strategic Communication: Getting Back to Basics. *Foreign Policy*. Retrieved from <https://foreignpolicy.com>
- Neuman, W. R., Guggenheim, L., Jang, S. M., & Bae, S. Y. (2014). The Dynamics of Public Attention: Agenda-Setting Theory Meets Big Data. *Journal of Communication*, 64(2), 193–214. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcom.12088>
- Ohmae, K. (1990). *The Borderless World*. London: Collins
- Ohmae, K. (1995). *The End of the Nation State*. New York: Free Press
- Paulus, A., & Vashakmadze, M. (2009). Asymmetrical war and the notion of armed conflict – a tentative conceptualization. *International Review of the Red Cross*, 91(873), 95–125. <https://doi.org/10.1017/s181638310999018x>
- Paletz, D. L., & Schmid, A. P. (1992). *Terrorism and the Media*. SAGE Publications, Incorporated.
- Pampalone, T. (2020a, January 16). Watch Your Language: How English is Skewing the Global News Narrative. *Global Investigative Journalism Network*. Retrieved from <https://gijn.org>
- Pampalone, T. (2020b, January 16). Watch Your Language: How English is Skewing the Global News Narrative. *Global Investigative Journalism Network*. Retrieved from <https://gijn.org>
- Pinch, T. (2008). Technology and institutions: Living in a material world. *Theory and Society*, 37(5), 461–483.
- Pieterse, J. N. (1995). Globalization as hybridization. In M. Featherstone, S. Lash, & R. Robertson (Eds.), *Global modernities* (pp. 45–68). London: Sage.
- Plessner, H. (1970). *Laughing and crying: A study of the limits of human behaviour*. Evanston, IL: Northwestern University Press.
- Prichard, P. (1987). *The Making of McPaper: The Inside story of USA Today*. Kansas City, MO: Andrews, McMeel and Parker.
- Rammert, W. (2012). Distributed agency and advanced technology. In J.-H. Passoth, B. Peuker, & M. Schillmeier (Eds.), *Agency without actors?* (pp. 91–112). New York, NY: Routledge.
- Reese, S. D. (2007). The Framing Project: A bridging Model for Media Research revisited. *Journal of Communication*, 57(1), 148–154. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2006.00334.x>

- Ritzer, G. (1996). *The McDonaldization Thesis: Is expansion inevitable?*. SAGE Social Science Collection.
- Robertson, R. (1995). Glocalization: Time- Space and Homogeneity-Heterogeneity. In M. Featherstone, S. Lash and R. Robertson (ED.), *Global Modernities* (pp. 25-44.) London: Sage.
- Robertson, R. (1992). *Globalization: Social Theory and Global Culture*. London: Sage.
- Rosner, S. (2017, May 11). Opinion | The People vs. Haaretz. The New York Times. Retrieved from <https://www.nytimes.com>
- Sacks, H., Schegloff, E., & Jefferson, G. (1978). A simplest systematics for the organization of turn-taking in conversation. In J. Schenkein (Ed.), *Studies in the organization of conversational interaction* (pp. 5–56). New York, NY: Academic Press.
- Sakr, N. (2007). Challenger or lackey? The politics of news on Al-Jazeera. In D. K. Thussu (Ed.), *Media on the move: Global flow and contra-flow* (pp. 116–132). London: Routledge.
- Schlesinger, P. (1991a). *Media, State and Nation: Political Violence and Collective Identities*. SAGE Publications Limited.
- Schlesinger, P. (1991b). *Media, State and Nation: Political Violence and Collective Identities*. SAGE Publications Limited.
- Schlesinger, P., Murdock, G., & Elliott, P. R. C. (1983). *Televising “terrorism”: Political Violence in Popular Culture*. Marion Boyars.
- Schulz, W. (2004a). Reconstructing Mediatization as an Analytical Concept. *European Journal of Communication*, 19(1), 87–101. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0267323104040696>
- Schulz, W. (2004b). Reconstructing Mediatization as an Analytical Concept. *European Journal of Communication*, 19(1), 87–101. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0267323104040696>
- Schulz, W. (2004c). Reconstructing Mediatization as an Analytical Concept. *European Journal of Communication*, 19(1), 87–101. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0267323104040696>
- Schutz, A., & Luckmann, T. (1984). *The structures of the life-world I*. Evanston, IL: Northwestern University Press.
- Schutz, A., & Luckmann, T. (1989). *The structures of the life-world II*. Evanston, IL: Northwestern University Press.
- Schiller, H.I. (1985). Transnational media and national development. In K. Nordenstreng and H.I. Schiller (ED), *National Sovereignty and International Communication*. Norwood, NJ: Ablex

- Semetko, H. A., & Valkenburg, P. M. (2000a). Framing European politics: A Content Analysis of Press and Television News. *Journal of Communication*, 50(2), 93–109.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2000.tb02843.x>
- Semetko, H. A., & Valkenburg, P. M. (2000c). Framing European politics: A Content Analysis of Press and Television News. *Journal of Communication*, 50(2), 93–109.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2000.tb02843.x>
- Semetko, H. A., & Valkenburg, P. M. (2000c). Framing European politics: A Content Analysis of Press and Television News. *Journal of Communication*, 50(2), 93–109.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2000.tb02843.x>
- Semetko, H. A., & Valkenburg, P. M. (2000d). Framing European politics: A Content Analysis of Press and Television News. *Journal of Communication*, 50(2), 93–109.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2000.tb02843.x>
- Semetko, H. A., & Valkenburg, P. M. (2000e). Framing European politics: A Content Analysis of Press and Television News. *Journal of Communication*, 50(2), 93–109.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.2000.tb02843.x>
- Searle, J. (1995). *The construction of social reality*. New York, NY: Free Press.
- Scheufele, D. A. (1999). Framing as a theory of media effects. *Journal of Communication*, 49(1), 103–122. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1460-2466.1999.tb02784.x>
- Signorielli, N. (1990). Television's Mean and Dangerous World: a continuation of the cultural indicators perspective. In N. Signorielli and M. Paletz, David L., & Schmid, Alex P. (Ed) (1992) *Terrorism and the Media*, Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Slater, J. (2007). Muting the Alarm over the Israeli-Palestinian Conflict: *The New York Times* versus *Haaretz*, 2000–06. *International Security*, 32(2), 84–120.
<https://doi.org/10.1162/isec.2007.32.2.84>
- Smith, P. (1997). *Millennium Dreams*. London: Verso.
- Soeffner, H. G. (1997). *The order of rituals: The interpretation of everyday life*. New Brunswick, NJ: Transaction.
- Sniderman, P. M., Brody, R. A., & Tetlock, P. E. (1993). *Reasoning and Choice: Explorations in Political Psychology*. Cambridge University Press.
- Stanley, C. (1972). *Folk Devils and Moral Panics*. London: MacGibbon & Kee.
- Thussu, D. K. (2000). *International communication: Continuity and change*. Cambridge: Polity Press.
- Tajfel, H. (1982). Social Psychology of Intergroup Relations. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 33(1),

1–39. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ps.33.020182.000245>

Thompson, J. B. (1994). Social theory and the media. In D. Crowley, & D. Mitchell (Eds.), *Communication theory today* (pp. 27–49). London, England: Polity.

Tomlinson, J. (1991). *Cultural imperialism*. London: Pinter Press.

Tovy, T. (2015). The Changing Nature of Geostrategy 1900-2000 - The Evolution of a New

Tsoref, A. (2010, June 3). 3 most viewed YouTube clips in the world - posted by IDF - Haaretz Com. *Haaretz.com*. Retrieved from <https://www.haaretz.com>

Thussu, D. K. (2007). Mapping global media flow and contra-flow. In D. K. Thussu (Ed.), *Media on the move: Global flow and contra-flow* (pp. 11–32). London: Routledge.

Tuchman, G. (1978). *Making news*. New York: Free Press.

Tuchman, B. W. (1989). *A Distant Mirror: the calamitous Fourteenth century*.

<https://ci.nii.ac.jp/ncid/BA29381861>

VanLoon, J. (2008). *Media technology: Critical Perspective*. Maidenhead, England: Open University Press.

Watzlawick, P., Beavin, J. H., & Jackson, D. D. (1967). *The pragmatics of human communication*. New York, NY: Norton.

Watts, M., Domke, D., Shah, D. V., & Fan, D. P. (1999). Elite Cues and Media Bias in Presidential Campaigns. *Communication Research*, 26(2), 144–175.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/009365099026002003>

Weber, M. 1. (2021). *Politics As a Vocation*. Hassell Street Press.

Wessler, H., & Adolphsen, M. (2008). Contra-flow from the Arab world? How Arab television coverage of the 2003 Iraq war was used and framed on Western international news channels. *Media, Culture, and Society*, 30(4), 439–461.

Wendt, A. (1999). *Social Theory of International Politics*. Cambridge University Press.

WION. (2021, May 19). How representative is Hamas of Palestinians? WION. Retrieved from <https://www.wionews.com>

Wijninga, P., Osterveld, W., Galdiga, J., & Wessler, H., & Adolphsen, M. (2008). Contra-flow from the Arab world? How Arab television coverage of the 2003 Iraq war was used and framed on Western international news channels. *Media, Culture, and Society*, 30(4), 439–461.

White, D. (1950). The “Gate Keeper”: A Case Study in the Selection of News. *Journalism Quarterly*,

27(4), 383–390. <https://doi.org/10.1177/107769905002700403>

Woods, J. (2011). The 9/11 effect: Toward a social science of the terrorist threat. *Social Science Journal*, 48(1), 213–233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soscij.2010.06.001>

Yarchi, M. (2014). “Badtime” Stories: The Frames of Terror Promoted by Political Actors. *Democracy and Security*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17419166.2013.842168>

Yarchi, M. (2016). Terror Organizations’ Uses of Public Diplomacy: Limited versus Total Conflicts. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 39(12), 1071–1083. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610x.2016.1184064>

Yarchi, M., & Ayalon, A. (2020a). Fighting over the Image: The Israeli – Palestinian Conflict in the Gaza Strip 2018 – 19. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 46(2), 123–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610x.2020.1751461>

Yarchi, M., & Ayalon, A. (2020b). Fighting over the Image: The Israeli – Palestinian Conflict in the Gaza Strip 2018 – 19. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 46(2), 123–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610x.2020.1751461>

Yarchi, M., & Ayalon, A. (2020c). Fighting over the Image: The Israeli – Palestinian Conflict in the Gaza Strip 2018 – 19. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 46(2), 123–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610x.2020.1751461>

Yarchi, M., & Ayalon, A. (2020d). Fighting over the Image: The Israeli – Palestinian Conflict in the Gaza Strip 2018 – 19. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 46(2), 123–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610x.2020.1751461>

Yarchi, M., & Ayalon, A. (2020e). Fighting over the Image: The Israeli – Palestinian Conflict in the Gaza Strip 2018 – 19. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 46(2), 123–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610x.2020.1751461>

Yarchi, M., & Ayalon, A. (2020f). Fighting over the Image: The Israeli – Palestinian Conflict in the Gaza Strip 2018 – 19. *Studies in Conflict & Terrorism*, 46(2), 123–136. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1057610x.2020.1751461>

Young J. (1971). The role of the police as amplifiers of deviance, negotiators of reality and translators of fantasy. In Cohen S. (Ed.), *Images of Deviance* (27–61). Harmondsworth: Penguin.

Zaller, J. R., & R, Z. J. (1992). *The Nature and Origins of Mass Opinion*. Cambridge University

Press.

Zehorai, I. (2018, January 24). The Richest Terror Organizations in the World. Forbes. Retrieved from <https://www.forbes.com>

APPENDIX 1 - CONTENT ANALYSIS MEASURE FOR FRAMES

Content Analysis Measure for frames was developed by Holli Semetko and Patti Valkenburg to identify and analyze frames present in the press coverage of an issue to measure the extent to which a frame appears within the content. Coders must answer yes or no to a series of questions set as sub-categories within a frame. These questions are as follows.

1- ATTRIBUTION OF RESPONSIBILITY

- Does the story suggest that some level of gov't has the ability to alleviate the problem?
- Does the story suggest that some level of the government is responsible for the issue/problem?
- Does the story suggest solution(s) to the problem/issue?
- Does the story suggest that an ind. (or group of people in society) is resp. for the issue-problem?
- Does the story suggest the problem requires urgent action?

2- HUMAN INTEREST FRAME

- Does the story provide a human example or "human face" on the issue?
- Does the story employ adjectives or personal vignettes that generate feelings of outrage, empathy-caring, sympathy, or compassion?
- Does the story emphasize how individuals and groups are affected by the issue/problem?
- Does the story go into the private or personal lives of the actors?
- Does the story contain visual information that might generate feelings of outrage, empathy-caring, sympathy, or compassion?

3- CONFLICT FRAME

- Does the story reflect disagreement between parties-individuals-groups-countries?
- Does one party-individual-group-country reproach another?
- Does the story refer to two sides or to more than two sides of the problem or issue?
- Does the story refer to winners and losers?

4- MORALITY FRAME

- Does the story contain any moral message?
- Does the story make reference to morality, God, and other religious tenets?
- Does the story offer specific social prescriptions about how to behave?

5- ECONOMIC FRAME

- Is there a mention of financial losses or gains now or in the future?
- Is there a mention of the costs/degree of expense involved?

-Is there a reference to economic consequences of pursuing or not pursuing a course of action?

